

**A Thesis
On**

**CHANGE FROM RESIDENTIAL USE INTO COMMERCIAL: A
CASE STUDY OF SINAMANGAL LANDPOOLING AREA**

Submitted to:

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Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science in Urban Design and Conservation

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis work entitled “**CHANGE FROM RESIDENTIAL USE INTO COMMERCIAL: A CASE STUDY OF SINAMANGAL LANDPOOLING AREA**” in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of is an original report of my research, has been written by me and has not been submitted for any previous degree. The research work is almost entirely my own work. Due reference has been provided to all supporting literature and resources.

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Recommendation

This is to certify that this thesis work entitled “Change from Residential into Commercial: A Case Study of Sinamangal Landpooling” submitted by Mr. Sudip Nepal is a bonafide thesis work carried out under my/our supervision and guidance and fulfilling the nature and standard required for the partial fulfillment of the degree of Master of Science in Urban Design and Conservation. The work embodied in this thesis has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

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Certificate of Approval

The undersigned certify that they have read, and recommended to the Purbanchal University, Khwopa Engineering College (KhEC) for acceptance, a thesis report entitled “**Change from Residential Use into Commercial: A Case Study of Sinamangal Land Pooling Area**”. Submitted by Sudip Nepal, in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of “Master of Science in Urban Design and Conservation”.

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Abstract

Change in urban land use is a global phenomenon occurring over time. In a developing country like Nepal, using a residential property for commercial purposes has become a popular choice for thousands of people living in urban areas which is a cost-effective and time-saving option. The aim of the study is to find the influencing factor and impact due to change in use from residential into the commercial in the Sinamangal Landpooling area especially designed and approved for the residential purposes by the Government of Nepal which reflect the less understanding of the market forces and future trends by the planning authority. The purpose and intent of the Land pooling project have not been met.

Among the different factors for the increase in the commercial activities profit maximization and the population growth and demands are the major factors for the change in use. Due to the increase in the encroachment of commercial activities in the major as well as in the residential street causes overstretching of infrastructure, lack of parking space, Overcrowding, abuse of planning standards, high increase of the property value etc. destroying the peaceful residential environment. If the raising pressure on commercial land use is not controlled and maintained the commercial use will be sprawling all over the area contributing to the rapid decaying of the planned area (urban fabric) and making the LP techniques failures in the future.

To control the haphazard development of the commercial use in the LP area, the policy needs to be updated or modified in order to incorporate the other aspects of the planning as well as the inhabitants and the local government of the area should be actively involved and control the extensive use of the commercial activities to make the peaceful living environment. Moreover, Land pooling area should be designated as a "comprehensive development zone". Then, planning standards and Urban design guidelines should be created to create a better urban environment.

Keywords: *Land pooling, Land Use Change, Zoning, Commercial Use, Residential*

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List of Abbreviations

BS	Bikram Samvat
CBD	Central Business District
DDA	Delhi Development Authority
DEs	Developer Entities
DPR	Detailed Project Report
DPR	Detailed Project Report
EDC	External Development Charge
EWS	Economically Weaker Section
FAR	Floor Area Ratio
GIS	Geographical Information System
GLD	Guided land Development
GoN	Government of Nepal
HFL	High Flood Level
HIPC	Highly Indebted Poor Country
HIPC	Highly Indebted Poor Country
IDP	Integrated Development Plan
KII	Key Informant Interview
KMC	Kathmandu Metropolitan City
KVDA	Kathmandu Valley Development Authority
KVTDC	Kathmandu Valley town Development Committee
LIG	Low Income Group
LP	Land Pooling
NEA	Nepal Engineering Association
NNBC	Nepal National Building Code
OSR	Open Space Ratio
PSP	Public Semi-Public
STP	Sewerage Treatment Plant
SWM	Solid Waste Management
UD	Urban Design
ZDP	Zonal Development Plan

Chapter One

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Land use changes are a long-term, worldwide process that can be seen in a specific metropolitan center on a small or large scale (Raharjo, 2005). Concern over the factors affecting the spatial organization of a metropolitan area's economy, demographics, and environment has led to the current rise in interest in studying land use successions. The percentage of the population that resides in settlements designated as urban areas, typically seen as directly tied to economic development, is known as urbanization. Urban sprawl and densification have resulted from the fast urbanization and growth in the urban population as well as the rising demand for housing and infrastructure in the majority of the world's cities.

Like other countries, Nepal is also facing the problem of urbanization, especially, Kathmandu valley has been undergoing rapid urbanization for three decades resulting in haphazard sprawl growth. According to the census preliminary report 2021, the population of Nepal has reached 29,192,480. In 2021, the urban population has reached 66.8% and Kathmandu metropolitan city has the highest population of 8, 45,767 and the highest population density of 5,108 persons per square kilometer with an urban growth rate of 6.5%.

Urbanization has been mismanaged and haphazard due to the rapid growth in population and more people are migrating to the major cities like Kathmandu, Bhaktapur, Pokhara, Butwal, and making them more populous. An increase in poverty, a lack of education, and employment opportunities in rural areas are key motivators for people to relocate from rural to urban areas. As more people migrate to urban areas due to the availability of different facilities and opportunities generated by the city, high concentration of commercial and employment opportunities, higher-order education, transport, and health facilities, income levels tend to rise as more jobs and opportunities are available due to the economic activity and unstable political situations which contribute to the rapid urbanization.

With the rapid growth of the urban population and the resulting human activities, there is pressure on the limited urban land. With the increased pressure of demand for land, it will be difficult to implement the rules and regulations that will make land administration more complex. This haphazard growth in the area has caused a physical change in the city area and the lives of the local people have been affected. Thus, the increase in the population of the city has led to the congestion and densification of the historic core areas of Kathmandu which consist of old traditions and heritage buildings, and also Creates a city poor living environment, lack of infrastructure, traffic congestion, etc., as well as becoming more vulnerable to disaster. Land demand is increasing day by day exponentially due to the excessive inflow of people.

With the increasing population, the agricultural land is converted into an unplanned residential area. The unplanned growth of urbanization in the town will create severe problems for the people residing there. The housing condition, as well as the living condition of people, is deteriorating day by day such as an increase in the slump, and squatter settlement are increasing and are characterized by an acute shortage of water supply, congestion, environmental pollution, poor sanitation, and lack of proper infrastructure and open spaces.

Thus, the residents are forced to live in unfavorable conditions. Due to the congestion and unavailability of land, the land price has gone to the peak in the core area during the decades. The urban fringe areas being less expensive and wanting people to build their own homes have shifted the people to the periphery of the metropolis. If the proper planning interventions are not taken promptly it will face the consequences of unplanned urban growth as the other city in the country. There is a need for land development techniques and urban planned environmentally friendly design concepts.

There are several efforts from the government and private sector to solve the housing problems in Kathmandu. New urban space has been developed day by day. To meet the housing needs of the people and to control haphazard urbanization government has launched different land management techniques including the land pooling project. Thus, land development acts as an alternate solution to a needed change in lifestyle. In Nepal three form of land development has been adopted which are site and service, Guided land development (GLD), and land pooling (LP) as an attempt to control the haphazard unplanned growth development of the area and to develop the fringe area in a planned way. All three land development techniques have been tried and have mixed success. The land pooling project is more popular among other land management techniques which have been adopted by the government of Nepal. So, the area can be developed in a planned way with the availability of different facilities, open spaces, drainage facilities, and infrastructures. The increased population can reside in this planned area.

To accommodate the housing need of the increasing population of the city and to develop the fringe area in a planned way the land pooling project has been adopted by the government of Nepal. As we know cities are dynamic in nature. It tends to grow and change because of the multitude of actions of its various parts at a variety of scales. Thus, change in residential use is the most commonly seen in developing countries like Nepal. Using the residential property for commercial purposes has become a popular choice for thousands of people living in urban areas in Nepal. A cost-effective and time-saving option, you can use your residential property for commercial purposes, to effectively work from home and earn money. But Land pooling is a technique which is originally designed for residential purposes, the road networks, blocks, open spaces, and other infrastructure facilities are designed for residential purposes with few commercial activities.

But there is an unusually rapid commercial activities development scenario on the land pooling area which is more concentrated on commercial activities and is being evolved as a commercial hub rather than a residential area which will ultimately affect the inhabitants of the area. The residential spaces are being used for commercial activities.

So, this research will focus on the conversion of the land pooling area originally designed for residential purposes into a commercial hub by examining the case of Sinamangal Landpooling area. It will also try to understand the reasons for developing the area into a commercial hub and its impact on the surrounding environment, inhabitants, and the neighborhood.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A major problem of rapid urban growth is changing the land use pattern which includes a rampant change in land and building use. Commercialization of the residential properties is spreading at an alarming rate, particularly in urban areas. Commercialization in unplanned settlements or old established areas is not new to use but in the case of planned and approved housing schemes, it is something that reflects that immaturity on the part of planning and development controlling agencies about their expertise in understanding the market forces and future trends.

The study area is a land pooling that is designed and planned for residential purposes. The development in this area is different from the other land pooling areas. Unplanned commercial development has trickled down to the main and sub roads of planned housing schemes in this area. The use of building for residential purpose is in decreasing phase whereas building used for a commercial purpose is increasing and most of the other plot has been occupied by temporary commercial activities. There is also an increasing trend that the residential building being occupied and or converted for commercial activity or mixed use in a haphazard manner. The area has more commercial activities this will ultimately convert the residential purposes area into a commercial hub. Commercial activities include not only shops, plazas, markets new office blocks, commercial places (lodges, guest houses, and hotels), groceries, restaurants, bars, banks, offices, furniture factories, grill factories, etc. but also private sector educational and health institutions, offices, banks, beauty clinics, gymnasium, clubs, and similar other uses placed haphazardly in the residential area creating the different problems to the residents of the area.

Haphazard commercialization in these residential areas is leading to adverse land use, and environmental, and socio-economic impacts affecting human health and privacy. Any such commercial development causing adverse impacts can undoubtedly be termed unsustainable development. This change will impact and challenge the overall city-built environment which includes poor solid waste management, inadequate parking space, noise pollution, and the overstretching of infrastructure services. The change in residential use especially to commercial use in speed and scope has presented negative consequences of housing

shortage, traffic congestion, parking problem, insecurity, and social vices. The uneven cost of residential accommodation as well as the reduction of environmental qualities such as noise and air pollution is well associated with this development. It will also make the inhabitants shift to the new residential neighborhood for a peaceful living environment and will promote the urban sprawl in the outer fringe area. Not only does the conversion of land from residential to commercial affect service delivery, but it also results in the escalation of residential property prices.

The demand for commercial areas needs to be met in a planned manner. Otherwise, this TSUNAMI of commercialization will destroy the tranquility and livable environment of the residential area and there will be hardly any place anyone can live, be sure that tomorrow it will still be a residential area.

The land use change from residential to commercial, this development could pose a concomitant challenge for urban planning, the planning authority, service provider, and residents. Why have the concerned regulatory agencies failed to ensure the planned growth of commercialization in the LP area? The answer to this question lies in a complex of institutional obstacles to the functioning of these regulatory agencies. These obstacles range from weaknesses in the forecasting of future demand of commercial areas and rigid.

Furthermore, these changes could pose a challenge to development control and compromise the efforts of the planning process. There are also complex obstacles to ensuring the planned development of commercial activities in the new planning area

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the research is to understand the change in the use of a residential area for commercial use in planned Land pooling areas. These rampant commercialized activities are increasing in this area. More specifically the study seeks to understand the government-adopted land management technique i.e., land pooling which is originally designed and planned to provide living space for residential purposes and conversion to commercial use its causes and impact are also studied. So, the main objectives of this research are:

1. To identify factors that influence change in the use of a residential area into a commercial area originally designed and planned for residential purposes?
2. To find out the positive and negative impact in the area due to the rise in commercial activities.

1.4 Significance of the study

To control the hazardous development in the fringe area, the government adopted the land management technique i.e., land pooling to develop the unused land area into a planned settlement for the residents' purposes and to provide living space for the residents and to meet the housing needs of the increased population of the city in the planned way with providing the different infrastructures, facilities, and services.

Different studies have been carried out on the completed land pooling project but the emergence of the Sinamangal land pooling project as a commercial hub has not been carried out so far. This study will focus on the use change and rise of commercial activities in the residential land pooling project emerging as a new commercial hub in the city. This rapid change in the change in use of buildings and the increase in commercial activities on every corner and street of the neighborhood etc. without reference to any planning or assigned function are destroying the characteristics of planned areas in the city. The change in use, development pattern, causes, and impact of commercial activities on the inhabitants will be studied in detail so that this study will help to guide the urban planner, planning authority and the land pooling developer to consider and developed the commercial activities in a planned way. The demand and forecast of the commercial activities should be met in the planned way.

This study will also help make aware the authority of this concern and to take control and regulate this raising issue so, that the purpose and intent of the land pooling project will be met and will be able to make an inclusive and sustainable planned city. This study will also develop restrictions on certain use of commercial activities and to make think about the mechanism, policies, and guidelines to regulate and enhance the development controls. The study will identify and give insight into some of the best practices adopted by the other country in the LP project to control the change of use and plan different commercial, institutional, industrial, recreational, etc. in a planned way.

The findings of this research will thus contribute to and make aware to the developers and planning authority to make think of the planned neighborhood by incorporating different planning parameters in the land pooling projects rather than vehicular access and a regular plot. So, the land pooling area is developed in the planned way with residential area, commercial area, recreational area, industrial area, etc. The finding will also be relevant to find out the causes and impact of the increase in commercial activities and the need and necessity of the development controls guidelines and regulations in the LP area and will provide a basis for further research. This is particularly important as the approach will also be of value to City Planning Department (KVDA) in its decision-making on the land Pooling project.

1.5 Rationale of the Study

A large of studies have been carried out in distinct aspects of the ongoing and competed Land pooling project. The Land pooling project study includes a study on the land pooling process, methods, benefits of the LP project, open spaces, facilities, etc. as per the prevailing trend. Post occupancy and Housing development has been recognized in some studies. But no study has come forward to define the change in use of the residential planned area for commercial use. Sinamangal LP project has been undertaken as there is rampant commercialization taking place in residential areas over the past few years. The study will be carried out in the detail about the conversion of the residential unit into a commercial hub, and its impact on the neighborhood. Studied have recommended policies to address the issues to manage the commercial needs and growing demands in the land pooling area in a planned way. This study aims to provide a new setting for the planned area.

1.6 Scope and limitation

The study will be based on secondary data, published books, articles, papers, manuals, and literature Reviews. The Literature review includes the collection and review of different case studies and scenarios in a change of use of residential areas into commercial use in different Nations and International cases. Based on the studied different findings for factors and impact of change in use and how these haphazard commercial activities issue has been addressed in the other country Land pooling policy is reviewed and made a recommendation for revision on the land pooling policy to incorporate the other planning aspects.

Apart from the review of the Case study, Land pooling policy, a field survey will also be carried out on the Sinamangal inhabitants, and the planning authority (KVDA), individuals with expertise in Land pooling area, etc. will be interviewed to know their views and suggestion in this case. The study will recommend on this basis to prepare and revise the land pooling policy to incorporate the other aspects of the planning parameter in the Land pooling (LP) Project and to prepare and develop the regulating guidelines to control the haphazard commercial use in the planned area to make suitable area for living.

Chapter Two

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter reviews available literature about the research topic. The first part of the chapter discusses land use regulation and controls policy in Nepal. The second part includes the common type of change of use in neighborhood residential areas of cities around the world and their driving factors.

The implications of use change on the residents and urban planning are discussed in the third section. The last part focuses on the conceptual and theoretical framework for a change of land from residential to commercial use.

2.1 Land use policy 2015

2.1.1 Land use

Land use is one of the most important factors for city planning mapping. Based on the land use map prepared by the Department of Survey, Government of Nepal and different field studies, nine land use classes are considered (Figure 2.5), namely (i) built-up area; (ii) cultivation; (iii) plantation; (iv) open area; (v) water body; (vi) road; (vii) airport runway (viii) playground and (ix) sandy area. As most land use types in Kathmandu Metropolitan City are covered by built-up area and cultivation

Figure 2.1: Land use Map of Kathmandu Metropolitan City
(Source: Google Image)

According to the land use policy 2015 of Nepal residential zone and commercial zone are described as follows.

a) Residential Zone

The area of land used by people as their habitat is referred to as the "Residential Zone." Additionally, whether or not the land is adjacent to a house, this phrase also refers to a shed, bhakari (a sizable bamboo bin used to store crops), garage, stable, well, water tap, fruit or vegetable garden, yard, or other area used for similar reasons. This phrase also refers to a colony house, an apartment building in a residential area by a business entity or institution, and any location specifically designated as a residential area by the Government of Nepal (GoN), among other things.

b) Business Zone

"Business zone" refers to the area of land that is occupied by a building, hotel, exhibition center, gas station, go-down, a place for communicating or transacting goods, an association providing information and consulting services, haat (local marketplaces where a transaction is made regularly), disco operated for business purposes, club, swimming pool, theater hall including entertainment site, or any other business purpose. The phrase also refers to the property that a commercial building occupies that was built by a business company or organization in a business zone. Additionally, this term also refers to any region that the Government of Nepal (GoN) declares to be urbanized for market expansion and business purposes, among others.

2.2 Neighborhood

The area where people reside that has certain physical or sociological qualities is known as a neighborhood. According to Whittick (1974), a neighborhood unit is an integrated, planned urban area connected to the broader community of which it is a part and made up of residential areas, a school or schools, commercial centers, places of worship, open spaces, and possibly some service industry.

The most challenging type of land use in the area is frequently considered to be commercial growth. To meet the needs of people in the town and throughout a metropolitan area, there are many different types of commercial development. Commercial development occurs at different scales and locations depending on the local needs or market demand. The following groups these numerous commercial types:

a) Neighborhood Commercial

Residents of the immediate area may quickly access everyday necessities thanks to neighborhood commercial growth. A grocery store, bakery, local restaurant, drug store, video rental store, service station, daycare center, or some office space may be found in a neighborhood business district. For convenience and to offer one-stop shopping, these activities should ideally be concentrated in one area that is close to residential areas. Some neighborhoods are starting to allow mixed uses inside a focused "town or village center," featuring homes and/or offices above street-level stores, while others still require that the commercial parts fit in with the neighborhood's residential character.

b) Community Commercial

Community commercial development provides facilities, goods, and services that are required every week by the neighborhood or that are only possible with the help of the people as a whole (perhaps 3-5 neighborhoods). A very big grocery store, at least one other retailer (such as a huge discount store [K-Mart, Best Buy, etc.], hardware store, apparel store, or movie theater), restaurants, mid-size offices, and employers may all be found in a typical neighborhood commercial center. The huge mart, sarthi mart, and others are examples of this type of commercial development in Nepal.

c) **Regional Commercial**

Regional development offers "large ticket" products like furniture and appliances as well as a wide range of goods and services that the surrounding area (which has at least 100,000 inhabitants) needs on an irregular basis. A regional mall, hotels or motels, a sizable discount retailer (Home Depot), specialty dining, theater multiplexes, and other sizable entertainment facilities may be among the additional commercial uses in this kind of commercial development.

d) **Corridor Commercial**

The creation of commercial corridors frequently accommodates companies that require large display and storage areas while also offering goods and services to the visiting public. The length and depth of these centers must be controlled because these corridors are often highway-oriented to prevent the formation of wide, unsuitable, "creeping" strips.

Neighborhoods can decide what kind and how much commercial activity is required to serve their residents through the planning process. It's crucial to remember, too, that not every area needs to have each form of commercial development physically situated there. That much business activity cannot be sustained in any one community. (Neighbourhood Commercial Development, December 16, 1998)

2.2 Commercial Land Use

The tangible property that is attached to land for the express purpose of investing to increase capital in the form of profits or returns is known as commercial real estate (Hamza, 2014). Commercial land and property are classified as a type of real estate that is primarily intended for investment purposes by Abdusalam (2007). Commercial land use has been defined as locations used for trading activities, such as hotels, retail stores, gas stations, office buildings, warehouses, and department stores. These locations have been designed, constructed, and operated to realize a profit, either through the production of goods or the provision of services in the form of wholesale or retail outlets. It is expressed similarly as real estate created and run for investment, such as petrol filling stations, retail stores, showrooms, hotels, offices, and other structures or premises. purposes. Commercial land use is a parcel lot whose intention of use is either for retail or wholesale services (Online Business Dictionary, 2010).

2.2.1 Forms of Commercial Land Uses

- a) **Shops:** Shops include market shops, retail shops, and workshops to carry out business activities (Ogunsola, 2012). He further classified shops into:
 - i. **Comparative Shop:** these are business premises with products of long span which are made at random interims of materials for purchase, quality of products, price and marketing style for choice making.

- ii. **Convenience Shop:** these are residential outlets whose products are readily available at regular intervals for the patrons.
- b) **Offices:** These refer to offices as buildings specially constructed and designed for administrative functions, businesses, and service delivery.
- c) **Shopping Malls:** These are shopping centers with enclosed pedestrian halls.
- d) **Market Stalls:** This is a structure or open business premises on which products or services are bought or sold.

2.3 Commercial Land Development

The goal of commercial real estate development is to supply the space market with a new property that is more valuable than the costs of production. The idea was subsequently developed into the concept of an investment window that offers a feedback mechanism involving capital flows in the space market, which influences property values in determining new property added to the space market. The process of developing commercial real estate is a linear one that starts with the notion of producing a business asset and concludes with steady company activity. For the goal of intensifying or changing the use of land in order to produce new structures for commercial use, acknowledged operations including building materials, infrastructural services, personnel, financing, legality, and professional services are referred to as commercial property development.

2.4 Meaning of transformations

Transformations in urban environments have occurred in a variety of ways over time, including those relating to form size, land use, encroachments, structure heights, floor area coverage (in other words, unlawful constructions), and so on. This has also happened in the city's formal developments, which have proceeded outside of the legal framework. However, while the growth may not be in agreement with the city's planning guidelines, its very existence demonstrates its size. The following paragraphs highlight some of the major changes taking place in urban areas in general and in particular. (Afrin, Zerín, Sharmin, & Morshed, 2012).

a) Use affiliation

This kind of change entails increasing and enhancing non-residential usage in residential districts as well as additional applications in open space regions. This effect is most obvious in developments with lower plot sizes/units and along key transit corridors. About present demand, it can be explained as the invasion of stronger land uses over weaker land uses, which serves as a stimulant for land use expansion. For instance, in many metropolitan locations, residential buildings along the road or streets close to a planned market or business sectors are being turned into commercial spaces, and open spaces

are being encroached upon for housing, businesses, and other purposes. Economic considerations are the most significant aspect in this kind of situation apply pressure on transformation, where the value of economics outweighs that of habitation. (Afrin, Zerin, Sharmin, & Morshed, 2012)

b) Built form

The degree of consolidation, horizontal coverage, encroachments, structure quality, and streetscapes are used to gauge the shift. To satisfy their need for usable space, people frequently increase the covered area of the property. There are encroachments on public open spaces or the road to accommodate their needs. The planned structures' height transition is aided by the conversion of the residential apartments into commercial uses like retail stores and the accommodation of residential activities on an additional floor. This kind of informality can be found in formal communities that have sparsely populated sections that get harder to manage over time. Social pressures and the need to provide for an ever-growing population are the main drivers of this form of development accommodated in limited planned space. (Afrin, Zerin, Sharmin, & Morshed, 2012)

c) Time affiliation

This kind of transition is focused on alterations that take place over time. In terms of duration, informal development may be transient (and has since become permanent), persistent, or appear earlier than anticipated. Periodic markets, roadside petty sales, and other transient markets, for instance, are being transformed into permanent markets. Developments that are entirely or partially subject to land use- or ownership-related informality are referred to as having a permanent informality. Such transitions are influenced by both social and economic factors. (2012) Afrin, Zerin, Sharmin, and Morshed.

2.5 Urban land development in Nepal

The land is the primary prerequisite for any planning. Land development is a method of changing the current land use for other purposes. The land in Nepal is mostly under private ownership. 90% of the land for housing is still being supplied by the private sector and hardly the remaining 10% is catered to by public agencies through land development tools. Most private land development either organized or formal is limited only to land fragmentation and selling of the divided plots without any planning framework.

The land Development process in Kathmandu Valley

The Land development process in Nepal is carried out under two initiatives

a) Private sector

- a. Informal private sector – individual plots are bought and sold in which houses are built.
- b. Formal private sector – a large chunk of land is bought and clusters of land development.

b) Public Sector

2.5.1 Land Development tools

Once development begins, the process is difficult to stop. Often the interest of those who have already constructed buildings is to defeat the efforts to introduce urban planning. As development proceeds, these trends become more difficult to reverse and ultimately result in a poor urban environment being overcrowded, unhealthy uneconomic, and very expensive to services. Various methods have been developed and adopted to improve the ill effect of development which are

- (a) Site and services
- (b) Guided land Development and
- (c) Land Pooling

The government in Nepal has chosen to meet the need for urban land by executing site and services, land pooling, and guided land development schemes, carried out by its regional offices and local authorities. The first sites and services scheme was perhaps begun in the 1970s. When land pooling and guided land development became attractive, experts were brought to Nepal to conduct workshops that transferred practical knowledge of these strategies to the staff of the Department of Housing and Urban Development of the Ministry of Housing and Physical Planning.

2.5.2 Site and services

Site and Services are the traditional methods of land development. It is the process of assembling raw land and converting it into fully serviced plots before selling it to the beneficiaries with or without any subsidy. It was developed to provide serviced plots for housing to low-income groups in developing countries. In this method, the government purchases the entire land, and a new subdivision plan is prepared along with the sale and allotment of the new plots with a high level of basic infrastructures, such as water, roads, and sanitation facilities. This method was introduced to mitigate the problems faced by the vast majority of low-income families in the world building their shelter, which lacks basic hygiene, access, and electricity, the strategy was developed. During the 1970s and 1980s, sites-and-services schemes were implemented in nearly 100 countries mostly on the behest of international agencies like the United Nations and the World Bank.

In Nepal three sites

- Kuleshwor (26.5 ha)
- Dallu (17.5 ha) and
- Galfutar (11 ha) was identified for, this program.

This project was targeted to supply housing plots for civil servants and employees of the government cooperation who did not own a house in Kathmandu valley. Dallu project was later converted into land pooling due to high resistance from the landowners.

2.5.3 Guided Land Development (GLD)

Guided Land Development (GLD) is an old concept that was formulated in Jakarta in 1970 for the development of the urban fringe. It was devised as a technique to enable the government to guide the haphazard development of private land around Jakarta.

In the method, the local landowners agree to invest a part of their land and contribute based on a pre-agreed layout plan. Ministry of Housing and Physical Planning 1988 introduced Guided Land Development (GLD) as a planning tool. It is a land management technique for guiding the conversion of privately owned land in the urban periphery from rural to urban uses. The simple concept of GLD is to encourage private developers and landowners to voluntarily contribute parts of their land for public use, such that the area becomes attractive for private investment for housing and other urban purposes. Thus, this approach can be regarded as an attempt to aggregate individual interests into a common community interest through technical support from the planning authorities. It is done in partnership with landowners who pay for the cost of servicing their land through the donation of land for public infrastructure and payment of betterment levy. It uses a combination of the traditional

The government's role is as a facilitator and provides technical support and providing infrastructures such as roads, drain, water supply, sanitation, electricity, etc., and enforcement of land subdivision regulations. The key advantage of the approach is that it is less costly than outright land acquisition and more equitable than land banking.

2.5.4 Land Pooling (or Land Readjustment)

Land pooling is “a technique for managing the planned development of urban fringe lands, whereby a government agency consolidates a selected group of land parcels and then designs, services and subdivides them into a layout of streets, open spaces and serviced building plots, with the sale of some of the plots for cost recovery and the distribution of the remaining plots back to the landowners to develop or to sell for development” (Archer, 1992b, p. 155). The concept of a land pooling scheme is regarded as one of the best readjustment techniques for the planned provision of urban environmental infrastructures and the supply of urban land without external investment (Oli, 2003). There are three basic components of land pooling as practiced in many countries.

- Consolidation of separate landholdings with the consent of a majority of landowners and leaseholders.
- Re-plotting design of land into building plots with the provision of road networks, and open spaces as prescribed by the specific rules and regulations.

- Construction of road network and public facilities, utilities, and selling plots to recover the development cost.

The concept of land pooling is guided by three keywords: unification, partnership, and land exchange (Archer, 1992). The term unification indicates the consolidation of the separate landholdings for the unified design, infrastructure provision and subdivision, and implementation of the project under single project management. The partnership indicates the partnership between landowners for the equitable sharing of the costs and benefits of the development.

Land pooling project is one of the most viable urban land management tools among the other two types i.e., site and services and Guided land development in Nepal because of the following merits.

- The project is completely community orientated and implemented with the coordination of the community.
- Huge amount of initial funds for land acquisition for the project is not required as land freely contributed for necessary roads, open spaces, and other community infrastructure.
- It is run by the fund arranged by selling reserved plots contributed by the community.
- The project is transparent to the community.
- Government acts as a facilitator.
- Optimization utilization of urban land.
- It helps to supply improved plots for housing in the market.
- Plots can be made available for a low-income group also.
- Urban services and facilities are equally available to all in the project area.

In order to construct a road in Pokhara, the concept of LP was first applied in Nepal in 1976. In order to acquire urban land, facilitate urban periphery, promote urban housing, and sustainably provide urban amenities, the Land Readjustment has evolved as an innovative, effective, all-inclusive urban development. The Land Pooling Projects in Nepal paint a clear picture of instances when LR has been implemented successfully in the Kathmandu Valley and throughout Nepal. After the successful pooling of Gongabu, Lubhoo, and Kamal Binayak, the LP/R was first started in Nepal's Kathmandu Valley in 1988. Liwali, Sintitar, Sainbu, Dalu, Nayabazar, Chabahil, Sinamangal, and Chiku Phant Kirtipur are just a few examples. Currently, 14 LP projects (total area: 352.8 ha; developed plots: 15,960) in the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal's largest urban region made up of 18 municipalities, including Kathmandu, have been finished or are almost finished. (Joshi, 2020) Similarly, 8 projects totaling 358.7 acres are in various phases of completion. The project area ranges from 5.4 hectares to 90.2 ha at its largest, with an average of 31.5 ha. In terms of global comparison, both at the project level and overall, the scope of LP in the Kathmandu Valley (or Nepal, for

that matter) continues to be modest. The Kathmandu Valley is not the only place in Nepal where LP initiatives have been carried out. (Joshi, 2020)

Land pooling schemes have been launched with the prime objective of providing developed plots with adequate provision of basic infrastructure services such as road, drainage, and water supply open space among others, in other a realize a planned urban expansion discouraging sprawl development.

2.6 Land Use Regulation 2079 BS

According to its geological capability, use, and features, the land has been divided into 10 zones by the government of Nepal under Land Use Regulation 2079 BS. By the new regulation, the land has been divided into a number of categories, such as agricultural zones, industrial zones, residential zones, commercial zones, industrial zones, areas of mines and minerals, forest zones, public use zones, areas of cultural and archaeological importance, and others.

This Act discourages unplanned development and selling of commercial land plots. Only places designated as residential zones are allowed to do so. The federal level of government will be in charge of land use mapping procedures for the nation, and it will then delegate authority to local governments for execution.

Local governments are permitted, by regulation, to alter, edit, and update the mapping as needed. Additionally, it says that a single land zone may contain subzones for the production of things like grains and fruits. The land use plan will be developed at the federal, provincial, and local levels. A provincial plan cannot be created that conflicts with a federal plan and a local plan cannot conflict with a provincial plan. The data achievement of the mapping must be maintained. Similarly, even though land classification can be changed with due process, the regulations prohibit using land that has been assigned to one category for another use.

If valuable minerals are discovered within the land use zone, if significant projects must be carried out there, or for any other reason imaginable, such as land needed for development, tourism, or world heritage sites, the federal government may also change the land use. The local level can change land usage to reduce catastrophe risk, relocate unsafe settlements, and establish the controls and standards required to monitor and govern land demarcation. Furthermore, there are plans in place to implement the land pooling scheme to mechanize agricultural land. The regulations provide the landowner the option to sue if they believe the classification to be improbable.

2.7 Kathmandu Valley Development Authority Act, 1988

Kathmandu Valley Development Authority was founded on April 13, 2012 by the Kathmandu Valley Development Authority Act, 1988. Its main goal is to create and carry out a Kathmandu Valley integrated

physical development plan. Under the heading "Operation of the Programs Related to Land Development Project," it performs the functions of a Land Pooling developer agency inside the Kathmandu Valley. It carries out all required Land Pooling procedures, including land selection, preliminary research, feasibility analysis, plan creation, plan implementation, and parcel redistribution. The statute mentions rules.

By Clause 9, Land Pooling Programs can only be implemented in areas where at least 51% of landowners or tenants have consented to them, which consist of at least 50 households. A User Committee is established in Clause 10, Sub-clause 1 to serve as a liaison between the landowners and the project management committee, which, while designing the land pooling project, discusses and offers feedback on all schemes, planning approaches, development of the physical infrastructure, contribution ratio, and land return activities and processes. After the land is chosen for the Land Pooling project, Clause 11, Section (7) of the Act prohibits any physical development for two years and ownership transfer for no more than one year. The Authority must transfer all the lands and temporary ownership as specified in Rule 11.

The Authority is required by Clause 12, Sub-rule 1, to submit an application to the relevant office for land survey and land revenue to obtain all necessary land documents, including a survey map and a landowner registration certificate in accordance with a provisional ownership certificate. Furthermore, in Sub-rule 2, the redistributed land papers will be legitimate, and the earlier ones will be regarded as invalid.

Under Clause 13, Part 10.1.4 of Subsection 10.1 of Section 10 of the Act, if the land is significantly reduced below the minimum plot area due to the contribution ratio and the owner is unable to purchase a site at a cost determined by the Authority, the Authority shall purchase the land of the such landowner or tenant and shall provide compensation in accordance with the current value of the said land.

If the user committee proposes to take over the development program, clauses 14 and 15 apply. The local entity managing the land development program in accordance with Subclause 1 shall receive technical and financial support from the Authority. Similar to that, for the committee to be effective, it must include at least 60% of the landowners or tenants.

2.8 Land pooling manual, 2072 BS

The New Town Development Project Nepal developed the Land Pooling Reference Manual (LPRM, 2072). This is an operating manual that contains all the requirements for the Land Pooling project. It covers a variety of elements, topics, and processes pertinent to land pooling projects, including the definition of land pooling, project management requirements, site selection, feasibility analysis, detailed planning methodology, amenities, design standards, financial investment, existing acts, regulations, and legal provisions, implementation strategies, project handover, monitoring, and project evaluation.

2.9 Building Regulation in Existing Residential Development (Building Bylaws)

Kathmandu city has its own building regulation based on its type of residential developments assessing low rise, and medium density. For the effective application of the regulations, the whole of Kathmandu city has been designated with different land use zones. The building design follows the building by-laws 2075 of the Municipality. There is different land use regulation to have controlled development.

Development plans that describe the goals and strategies for achieving future developments are a common component of development control. To direct the city in a planned and ordered manner, it also comprises a set of planning and building regulations. Master plans (zonal plans and detailed development plans), land use and building use, ground coverage, FAR, setback, open space, height and number of stories, parking requirements, etc. are all fundamental components of development control and apply to a variety of land developments as well as different types of buildings. The idea of development control is to limit how land and buildings are used and developed, as well as any significant changes to the way that land or buildings are already used. It is a crucial component of the process of planning. It aims to control a city's character, fabric, and personality as well as its growth and progress. Development controls comprise development plans regulations and guidelines aiming to achieve public health and safety, convenience, economic growth, and provision of efficient amenities and facilities. The controls are classified as:

a) Road width

To provide adequate infrastructure development and emergency services, the development should provide a sufficient road network. The regulatory provision has planned the width according to its length and character. The provisional length and width is depending on the accessibility to major road networks.

Table 2.1: Road width and length of road

Access Road width to be provided	Based on the length of the road
2m	50m
4m	200m
6m	1000m
8m	2000m
11m and above	More than 2000m

(Source: Building By-law 1993,)

b) Plot size

The acceptable minimum plot size has been established at 2.5 annas by the planning regulation. The concept is centered on offering a home setting that includes a parcel of land, infrastructure, and services. It is a crucial component of the housing standards. It is a strategy to influence housing density, manage costs, and recommend where a building should be located on a parcel of land. The size of the plot is a

factor in the cost of a unit of housing, affecting both the cost of the land and the cost of the infrastructure. (Mishra, 2019)

c) Density

It depends on occupancy standards, which are determined by the number of people per room. It has to do with the suggested amount of living space per person. The major goals of the floor area ratio (FAR), open space ratio (OSR), and height restriction are to control the density of residential development. In Kathmandu, traditional housing with three- and four-story buildings have been built to a high density of around 1000 people per hectare. According to the study, a gross density of roughly 500pp/ha is the economically ideal level. This level of density is conceivable in Kathmandu's current technological environment and is achievable with buildings that are one to three stories high. (Mishra, 2019).

d) Floor Area ratio (FAR)

Floor Area Ratio (FAR), which was amended in 2079, has a finite amount of infrastructure and resources. A Floor Area Ratio (FAR) is computed to prevent stress beyond what the city can handle. The Floor Space Ratio is another name for it. The ratio of the total covered area (real area) of all the floors to the total plot area is the simplest way to calculate it. $FAR = \text{Total area of all floors} / \text{Total Plot Area}$.

Permissible FAR and Maximum Height as defined by Kathmandu Municipality By-Laws 2079

Table 2.2: Permissible of FAR for the Commercial Sub Area by By-law 2079

S.N.	Description (Commercial Sub Area)	FAR
1	Residential/ Commercial (Mixed use)	4.5
2	Star Hotel	3.5
3	Commercial complex	3.5
4	School, College, University	2.5
5	Government and non-Government buildings	2.5
6	Cinema hall	2.5
7	Hospital and Nursing home	3

Source: (Kathmandu Metropolitan City, Building By-Laws2075)

Table 2.3: Dense Mixed-use residential sub-area FAR

S.N.	Description (Dense mixed-use Residential sub-area)	FAR
1	Residential Building	4
3	Commercial complex	3.5
4	School, College, University	2.5
5	Government and non-Government, Private buildings	2.5

7	Hospital and Nursing home	3
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Source: (Kathmandu Metropolitan City, Building By-Laws2075)

Table 2.4: Other Residential sub-area FAR

S.N.	Description	FAR
1	Residential Building	3.5
3	Commercial complex	3.5
4	School, College, University	2.5
5	Star Hotel	3.5
6	Government and non-Government, Private buildings	2.5
7	Hospital and Nursing home	3

Source: (Kathmandu Metropolitan City, Building By-Laws 2075)

e) Ground Coverage

The ground coverage of a building refers to the overall space that it occupies on the ground level. To make the most of the plot, the ground covering can be altered based on the height and FAR limits. By dividing the whole plot area by the building's ground floor area, the ground covering area is determined. Building area refers to a building's floor area when viewed from above.

$$\text{Ground Coverage Area (GCA)} = (\text{Building Ground Floor Area} / \text{Site Area}) \times 100$$

f) Setbacks

The open area between a building and a lot line or property line is known as a building setback. Only up to the setback line can the house be built. Again, this differs for various building kinds. The setback line is relevant to the entire building, not just the front. Another aspect that affects the setback line is the entire plot area.

g) Height Restrictions

The vertical distance between the average ground level and the highest point of a building is its height. Keep in mind that the height of your home will not be affected by the presence of a basement.

According to the building bye-laws, the maximum height of the building is governed by two factors.

- FAR
- Light plan

Even though FAR permits higher building height, the light plane factor restricts its height. As shown in the figure the maximum height of the building is not more than the height of the light plane.

Figure 2.2 : Light Plane to Restrict the height of building

2.10 Common types of change of land use and its impact in cities.

Several kinds of literature on change of use in different cities from both developed and developing countries have been reviewed.

2.10.1 Changing Dynamics of Land Use in Residential Neighborhood of Vani Vilasa Mohalla, Mysore

Shankar & D (2013) Vani Vilasa Mohalla is a residential neighborhood that experiences a rapid land use transformation. The changing dynamics of land use was emerging mixed land use in a residential neighborhood. The study shows that the increase in land-use change in residential areas is for the socio-economic benefits which are allowed by the locals and as well as by planning authorities initially making streets commercial streets. The study highlighted that residential use has decreased from 64.73 hectares to 63.40 hectares from 2009 to 2012 and from 74.40 to 64.73 from 1960 to 2009 respectively. The area under commercial use was 11.44 hectares. The areas allowed for commercial activities retail businesses, wholesale businesses, warehouses, shopping malls, cinema theatres, hotels, etc., and commercial use has increased from 6.05 hectares to 11.44 hectares from 1960 to 2012.

The study finds that this change in the residential area into mixed land use pattern is difficult to get alter and commercial activities have intruded into residential areas, especially along major roads. It affected greatly in terms of increasing the density of the area and overloading and mounted pressure on the existing infrastructure facilities like water supply, traffic, transportation, sewerage, etc. by changing the dynamics of land use.

The study concluded that mixed-use has positive and negative socio-economic and environmental impacts. Therefore, formulation of a balanced policy of mixed-use considering its environmental impact and socio-economic is needed for an hour. Only selective commercial/ Non-residential activity on residential premises should be permitted selectively and carefully, taking into consideration community needs, environmental impact, and provision for safe and easy traffic circulation and adequate parking. Thus, the City of Mysore experiencing changing dynamics in residential areas needs to be recognized and addressed properly by the Planning Authority in its development control regulations.

2.10.2 Change of Land Use from residential to commercial in Livingstone: Implication for Urban Planning

Mtawali (2019) evaluated the shift in Livingstone's land use and the effects it had on urban planning between 2009 and 2015. 50 out of 120 property owners who had changed uses were chosen using simple random sampling, and interviews with Livingstone City Council, ZESCO, and SWASCO were conducted with 5 key informants.

According to the study, the most common form of change of use was from residential to commercial (72%), then from residential to office (24%), and finally from residential to place of worship (12%). (4 percent). The biggest shift in use occurred in 2013, which was ascribed to the UN-WTO Conference's co-hosting, which increased demand for lodging. 44 percent of the properties whose use was altered from residential to another type did so back to residential usage. The decline that began in 2014 was linked to both the reduction in demand for lodges and guesthouses following the UN-WTO summit and the relocation of the provincial capital to Choma in 2012, where government meetings and workshops are currently held. Business owners faced a hurdle as a result of this. (Mtawali, 2019)

According to the report, business—primarily lodges and guesthouses—is the main driver of change of use in the City of Livingstone (70 percent). Other factors include the CBD's accessibility (16%) and rent value (14%), with uses like offices having higher rent values than residential ones. The effects on urban planning mostly relate to the provision of services and infrastructure, such as an increase in demand for services like power, water, road networks, and street lighting. Sixty-two percent of building owners had expanded and made changes to existing structures without upgrading the other infrastructure services, such as water, and electricity, to accommodate the new use. The domestic line is overloaded and becomes blocked, which has a further impact on urban planning. (Mtawali, 2019)

According to the study's findings, if a use change is not properly vetted, it might seriously complicate urban planning and cost the local government money to rectify any damage (Solid waste, drainage blockage, sewer blockage). One of the main recommendations is for Livingstone City Council to improve its development control mechanism, prevent sectorial planning, and make sure that other important institutions like ZESCO and SWASCO are involved in the processing of applications for change of land use. (Mtawali, 2019)

As cited in (Mtawali, 2019) In Zambia, although residential to commercial land use shifts in the city of Lusaka was first noted in the early 1980s, the situation in Zambia only got serious when President Mwanawasa led Zambia out of the category of Highly Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC) in 2002. This position indicated that, particularly in the city of Lusaka, the country's and its residents' social purchasing power was significantly improving (IMF, 2012). In the nation's capital city, both international and local businesses began to proliferate. The town core of the city quickly became home to hundreds of economic activities, making available commercial space insufficient. This caused several businesses to begin moving out of the CBD and towards the surrounding suburban communities of Fair View, Rhodes Park, Northmead, Long Acres, and Thorn Park. A scenario known as mixed land use became more prominent in the city as businesses moved from the CBD into residential districts, and the local government was forced to enact a rule that would control the change in land use (Simwanza, 2004). This led some firms to start leaving the

CBD for the nearby residential areas such as Fair View, Rhodes Park, Northmead, Long Acres, and Thorn Park. As the shifting of firms from the CBD into the residential areas increased, a situation known as mixed land use became pronounced in the city, and hence the local authority had no choice but to create a law, that would regulate the change of land use (Simwanza, 2004).

2.10.3 Physical Structure and Pattern of Land Use Changes from Residential into Commercial: Analyses of Mampang Prapatan, Jakarta, Indonesia

Raharjo, (2005) conducted a study on the physical structure and pattern of land use changes from residential to commercial in the Indonesian cities of Mampang, Prapatan, and Jakarta because residential to commercial land use changes affect both the land use pattern and the physical structures of residential areas. He examined the changes in land usage from 2004 to 2005. His research was inspired by and based on the fundamental principles of the land economy. He chose his study region, a residential neighborhood in Jakarta, the capital city of Indonesia since it had just seen a dramatic shift from residential to commercial land use. This is particularly clear not just along the major street of specifically in the vicinity of Mampang Prapatan VI's side streets.

According to the study's findings, land use changes in Mampang Prapatan VI involved both increases in construction intensity and changes in building function, from residential to commercial. These modifications exhibit commercial space in the form of multi-purpose structures that also house residences, as well as mixed-use structures that combine these two modifications. The study also found that among the most powerful influences on the land use changes that have taken place are the benefits of accessibility provided by the road function and a high degree of profit return. The adaptability of government policy and its incapacity to regulate these changes are further influencing elements. This development had a notable impact on the formal housing stock as well.

2.10.4 An Analysis of Residential-Commercial Land Use Changes in Lusaka City: What are its effects on formal Housing Stock?

Akakandelwa (December 2012), study shows that the formal housing stock in the city of Lusaka is examined about changes in residential and commercial land use. This study focuses on urban areas in the town center or CBD, such as Rhodes Park, Fair View, Northmead, and Thorn Park, where it has been noted that residential land use is constantly changing to accommodate other purposes, particularly commercial uses. Along Lusaka's main thoroughfares, including Addis Ababa Avenue, Independence Avenue, Church Road, Makishi Road, Great East Road, Bwinjifumu Avenue, and Katima Mulilo Road, economic activity has spread noticeably.

The primary reason for this is that Lusaka's central business district has been unable to keep up with the city's growing need for office space, traffic congestion, and insufficient parking spaces causing businesses to establish themselves in residential areas. Economic theory encourages this pattern when it indicates that other regions are growing economically as city activities are expanding to accommodate the tendency, areas near the CBD must be absorbed. Numerous private homes and vacant lots are gradually being transformed into commercial spaces, primarily for office use. The construction of contemporary office parks, hotels, executive residences, financial institutions (banks, insurance), and government complex offices distinguishes these surroundings.

According to survey results, factors that contribute to abrupt land use transitions from residential to commercial in Lusaka city include profit maximizing brought on by rising demand for commercial space uses and the physical aging of residential building structures that results in obsolesces. The analysis also shows that no effective regulatory framework or monitoring exists in the area to prevent modification of existing land use structures. For investors and developers, the increasing demand for commercial buildings in the region is a sign that the market for commercial real estate is booming. The market for residential real estate has been negatively impacted by this abrupt change in land use. The supply of residential properties has decreased as property developers focus more on developing commercial properties.

The negative repercussions that the city is currently experiencing as a result of this development of residential to commercial land use shifts include a decrease in the formal residential stock, high rental prices, physical development issues, developmental control challenges, and land misuse.

2.10.5 Analysis of Land Use Changes in Selected Cities in Nigeria

As cited by Mtawali, 2019, Egbenta (2009) examined and studied the factors that led to changes in urban land use, specifically in Nigeria's Enugu urban region between 1997 and 2008. According to the analysis, residential land usage in Enugu Urban abruptly changed to commercial use. The maximizing of the best return from the land was one of the driving forces behind this development, according to the study's findings. He encourages rational developers to be conscious of the effects of business cycles, since the demand for new buildings is extremely vulnerable to short-term output changes, and he suggests that there should be legislative frameworks for conversion in place.

According to Egbenta's research, other variables that contributed to the fast land use change in the city of Enugu included profit maximizing brought on by the rising demand for commercial uses and the physical aging and obsolescence of residential building structures. The study also demonstrated the absence of a robust legal framework in the study area that would have prevented the conversion of current land use structures. Investors and developers could tell there was a boom in the commercial real estate market by

the increasing demand for local commercial buildings. The market for residential real estate has been negatively impacted by this abrupt change in land use. The number of residential properties is declining as real estate developers focus more on developing commercial properties. An important highway, as neighborhoods have been changed into commercial areas.

This indicates that there are fewer residential properties available along Enugu's main highways, which is causing the rents for those that are available in other areas to increase. Due to the conversion of neighborhoods into commercial zones, these developments have harmed traffic congestion and the capacity of main roadways. (Mtawali, 2019)

Gwamna & Yusoff (2016), This study finds that the population increase, intra-urban migration, security and safety, public utilities, and environment and land use planning have a combined influence of 87% on land use change in the Kaduna metropolis. While land use change affects residential property values by 27% only and the other 73% is accounted for by other factors not included in this study.

2.11 Drivers of change of land use

Before looking at the influencing factors of land changes from residential to commercial, first, it is necessary to look at the framework and concept of land economics. Urban land use is determined by various factors such as the decisions made by households, the government (Primarily local authorities), and firms. One of the most important factors that can affect the development of a community is Sustainability. According to (Harvey, 1996), this is the process of making sure that products are easily accessible from strategic locations and the profit is maximized.

The concept of general accessibility refers to the cost associated with moving supplies (including time). For firms, this is the reason why they need public access to develop a production factor that is easy to access and easy access to the market. On the other hand, households need to have easier access to various facilities and workplaces, stores, schools, and recreation facilities. It is also largely dependent on the transport facilities. Another factor that needs to be taken into account is that Central Business Districts (CBD) offers great accessibility to customers. For CBD offices, location is the chief consideration in terms of labor supply. In addition, stores located in the CBD offer the highest income level capacity. Land limitations in CBDs and competition to get a site in a CBD location, result directly in higher rentals.

Secondly, special accessibility, or agglomeration economies, may influence the location decisions resulting from external economies of concentration or complementarity. It is the benefits that come when firms and people locate near one another together in cities and industrial clusters. This is a location placement decision that is influenced by the external economy, in terms of concentration and complementary elements between the businesses involved.

(Harvey, 1996) , finally notes that dynamic changes are the secular increase in real income and technology developments both have an impact on the pattern of land value. Such as new building techniques, which restrain ever-rising building costs, result in more intensive development in CBDs. When the increasing needs for particular land cause price hikes, this effect can be balanced to a large degree by the availability of the site or location. Relative land prices in sub-centers will increase, as in the city center, when people move to outlying suburbs, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 2.3: Change in land price Gradient
(Source: Harvey, 1996; 206)

In theory, three factors affect the location in terms of economic activities. These include rent, environmental factors, and accessibility. Dynamic variables and government policy are two more factors that are important.

2.12 Factors affecting land use change

Various studies have been undertaken to determine the elements that influence urban development patterns, taking into account the extent, rate, and impact of land use changes.

According to Farooq (2022), six basic factors that affect land use changes have been unified by conceptual reviews, along with additional factors like the desire for profit maximization among users of commercial space, ease of access in areas outside of central business districts, the growth of pollution, government land use policies, rising commercial space demand, and changes in location preferences. Some other factors that influence change that is complicated and intertwined.

According to the literature, the most frequently acknowledged responsible drivers of land-use changes include economic advancement, cultural, natural scientific, and technological factors, as well as public policies and globalization. Factors like the desire of business owners to maximize profits and the inability of central districts to control the growth of the economy cannot be ignored for land use change.

The summary of factors affecting use change from residential to commercial are as follows:

a. The Influence of Population on Land Use Changes

It has been proven through earlier studies that there is a very positive correlation between population density and land use changes. The rise in population also raises the demand for housing and business space, which has an impact on the types and amount of commercial property development in metropolitan areas. Changes in land use could occur from changes in the size and makeup of the local population, which are more likely to be influenced by economic activity.

b. Influence of Intra-Urban Migration on Land Use Changes

In their numerous studies, land economists, sociologists, and ecologists have expressed concern about the complexities of intra-urban mobility and how it affects changes in land use over time. Economists have assumed that business owners independently decide where to locate their operations based on factors such as the likelihood of achieving the maximum profit, ease of access, the availability of infrastructure facilities, and the availability of other goods that support their operations.

The cost of transportation, the closeness to customers, the rental value of the business space, the configuration of the space, the size of the space, the condition of the building, and the number and arrangement of shops, among other things, all have an impact on where a business will be located. Understanding the nature of changes in the spatial distribution of the urban space requires an understanding of the impact of intra-city migration. Intra-city mobility is essentially the key factor responsible for differences in the makeup of a given sector inside a metropolis. Population shifts cause variations in the rate of commercial real estate development and demand.

c. Influence of Security Facilities on Land Use Changes

One of the root causes of urban discontent and suburbanization has been crime rates. Commercial land users frequently pay a high price for land in a neighborhood with low crime rates in urban areas. Cities that are experiencing population loss are referred to as "shrinking urban centers".

Land use changes may be caused by a variety of circumstances, including population shifts in search of safer and more secure neighborhoods. Business owners are moving from one core district to another, as seen by the conversion of residential houses into commercial spaces. Crime can be seen as a disamenity that makes it difficult for commercial land users to operate in a particular neighborhood and motivates them to relocate to safer regions; as a result, those commercial properties that have been abated would be left vacant for other suitable land uses. Security and safety affect land values, and commercial land location decisions and ultimately influence land use changes.

The owners and tenants of commercial properties will see more significant changes if violence recurs in an urban region. Numerous studies have shown that cities with lower crime rates see less intra-city investment flow than do towns with higher crime records.

d. Influence of land use Control Measures on Land Use Changes

Due to the scarcity and fixed supply of land, it is essential that it be administered and managed in a way that assures sensible use by following planning standards to maximize returns for those who may generate benefits, profits, or other goods.

A city's population density can be changed by several zoning laws, with land use laws having the most power to change the urban region's overall land area. A decline in the total land use density in an urban center is a result of some land-use regulations. Planning policies that are effective and meaningful handle the problems linked with land uses in urban areas, which primarily include slum development, mixed land uses, environmental populations, congestion in transportation flows, and overpopulation. The implementation of sustainable city environments is facilitated by land use management measures, particularly development control, which also support the living standards of the urban population. It also contributes to urban residents' well-being, preventing spatial disorder brought on by mixed land use patterns.

Nevertheless, ineffective planning restrictions could result in disorderly urban land use. the chance that ineffective land use control mechanisms may lead to haphazard commercial land uses in an urban core, which will therefore harm the city's visual appeal.

e. Other Factors Influencing Land Use Changes

As cited by Farooq (2022), Lean (2005), and Sedney (2012), conclude from earlier research on land use changes that the following factors contribute steadily to the conversion of residential property to commercial land uses:

- (a) Urban population growth.
- (b) Increasing demand for commercial premises.
- (c) Failure of the central district to contain the growing economic activities,
- (d) Failure of land use control measures in its implementation.
- (e) Easy accessibility. Land use regulation.

These drivers of land use changes can best be diagrammatically represented below:

Figure 2.4 : Drivers of land use changes in urban centers

Source: As cited by (FAROOQ, 2022), Adopted from (Lean, 2005; Asamoah & Blessing, 2010; Sedney, 2012).

Other factors that could influence land use changes in an urban area are as follows:

- Site attraction is determined by factors like building design, site size, accessibility, complementary nature of uses, and neighborhood characteristics.
- Site functional capacity by the transportation infrastructure is a relevant variable.
- Neighborhood attractions; commute times to the city center; infrastructure; commercial activities; and types of offices and businesses.
- Socioeconomic class as the application variable is the land value inside the neighborhood where land use changes take place.
- Factors such as prime location, rising economic activity, rising commercial property rental values, ease in obtaining a business premise planning permit, and the presence of demand can influence changes in urban land use, especially from residential to commercial.

2.13 The Effects of Land use Changes from Residential to Commercial

It is impossible to overstate the negative effects of switching a piece of land from residential to commercial use. People who live nearby such locations are typically impacted by the mixed land use that emerges when land in residentially zoned regions is converted to commercial land use.

As Cited in Akakandelwa, (December 2012) Mathews, (2006)) In Sylvan, North Carolina, USA, performed research between 2004 and 2006 and discovered that most local meetings across the county frequently featured homeowner objections against proposed new neighboring commercial developments. One such instance is a zoning proposal for a modest commercial project that a resident argued should be rejected by the city council because it would negatively impact the quality of life of the neighborhood. Additionally, the locals argued that the commercial construction would dramatically lower property prices in the neighborhood, change the community's character, and have a detrimental impact on the value of their own properties.

In another instance, Raun (1997) adds that locals in the Omaha suburb of Nebraska objected to a commercial development near Lake Hastings. "Residents of the lake spoke out against the commercial development, claiming that it would lower their property values and quality of life. According to a local real estate broker, the development will harm owners of existing residential property. A neighborhood's desirability is more negatively impacted by commercial property adjacent than it is by a busy street.

The problem is not simple; rather, it is one of the fundamental problems of contemporary urbanization. A community design philosophy known as "new urbanism" supports the reintroduction of new home construction along with multi-use structures and housing that is grouped close to commercial service areas. New urbanisms assert significant benefits for this method of development, such as cheaper overall public infrastructure costs and a reduction in reliance on automobiles. Cited by (Akakandelwa, December 2012) (Mathews, 2006))

Some argue that converting land use from residential to commercial in a high-demand residential location may increase residential property prices by lowering the difficulty and expense of regular journeys. Convenience should increase the supply of residential properties, whereas unfavorable externalities should decrease the supply. Does the convenience of the change in land use from residential to commercial applications outweigh any negative externalities, increasing the implications for urban planning when it occurs too frequently in a neighborhood?

According to Asamoah (2010), as cited by Akakandelwa (December 2012), implications that come as a result of converting plots or already existing structures initially zoned for residential use include the following:

a. Reduction in formal housing stock

The number of residential homes that have been displaced by the new commercial blocks is not evenly distributed within the same location because changing land use from residential to commercial requires converting a residential plot of land or existing structure into commercial use, or existing commercial building. This will arise a shortage in overall housing stock in the city. In general, land that was intended for residential use has been drawn to industrial and commercial uses.

b. Development control challenges

Due to financial limitations, a lack of enforcement of development control laws, and insufficient public awareness of the activities, local authorities typically find it challenging to control these developments. This is because development must be monitored in areas where land use changes are occurring at an increasing rate (especially from residential to commercial). Additionally, because local governments can take longer than expected to approve requests for changes to land use, impatient developers often decide to develop their properties without permission.

c. Increase of economic activities in residential areas

Economic activity would tend to increase in residential areas and decrease in the CBD as more and more residential plots are converted to commercial plots as more and more people move out of the crowded town centers and into the residential districts. The provision of services in these locations is further harmed by this consequence. Shortage of parking spaces and traffic congestion are two of the biggest issues brought on by the adjustments.

d. Physical development challenges

Town residential areas are changing to meet the needs of the urban society as a result of rapid urbanization and the ensuing rise in the prevalence of commercial activities there. This is because residential areas have changed from being used for residential purposes to being used for commercial purposes (commercial). Since the region is neither a residential nor a commercial zone, many people indeed reject the rules and specifications given as planning in the long term.

e. High land values

Residential land is impacted because the conversion of land uses from residential to commercial takes place primarily within residential districts, which results in a shortage of space for residential accommodations. Residential land is under pressure in the study region because residential properties are being converted for commercial usage. Due to this shortage, land values are typically high and are expected to continue rising.

Rents are consequently far higher in the study area than they are in the city's other residential neighborhoods, where the land use change has had less of an impact. However, these higher returns

on land are welcomed by landowners. As a result, a lot of individuals are forced to relocate to hunt for land elsewhere since they are unable to afford the exorbitant rates. Since those who relocate from the Central Business District (CBD) will have to fight for property and housing towards the periphery, this practice undoubtedly has an impact on other places.

f. Abuse of land

Land conversion from residential to commercial use will result in an abuse of the property's carrying capacity because residentially zoned areas are smaller than commercial areas. The land on which the commercial business is located is frequently abused when a residential property, whose primary purpose is dwelling, is converted into an office. A parking area intended for, say, three automobiles would frequently have to accommodate six or eight vehicles.

g. Amenity effects of land-use regulations

Land use restrictions have an amenity effect in addition to the price and scarcity issues. Land use restrictions to preserve open space, groundwater supply, and quality, or to lessen noise, congestion, and pollution are all acceptable instances of amenity effects. Building limits, environmental zoning, limitations on the paint colors of houses, and even lawn mowing regulations that are implemented in some towns are examples of such regulations in residential neighborhoods.

2.14 Influence of Land Use Changes on Slum Formation in Urban Centers

As cited by Farooq (2022) Malpezzi & Maclennan (2001), stated that due to limitations in land use management measures that regulate changes in land use, the elasticity of the land supply varies in different cities. However, given that the residential property market in most emerging nations is so weak that people in the medium and lower income bracket are forced to live in substandard neighborhoods, this market scenario is unlikely to materialize.

According to an analysis done by Somik (2006) cited in Farooq (2022) on the impact of land use regulations on land use changes, as the socioeconomic activity of an urban center grows, homes on the outskirts of the central districts will be converted to commercial uses, which will reduce the supply of housing and further increase the rental value of residential properties.

As a result, people that fall into the middle class or lower will find it impossible to pay the exorbitant prices or rentals and would therefore turn to substandard housing. As illustrated in the following picture, an inelastic housing supply prevents the housing stock from expanding to accommodate the population boom. As a result, slum development is encouraged.

Figure 2.5 :Influence of land use change on slump formation in urban centers.
Source: (Farooq, 2022)

2.15 Conceptualizing Change from Residential to Commercial Use

A conceptual framework for changing a building's use from residential to commercial has been developed, according to an analysis of case studies from around the world as well as theoretical and conceptual frameworks on the subject. The idea states that the demand for commercial trading in cities is rising as a result of urbanization, which is one of the key factors influencing the change in usage. The notion of land economics suggests that commercial land has a higher value in terms of rent, necessitating the need to maximize profits as the other element.

In Zambia, governmental regulations like zoning also affect how uses are changed, and the Urban and Regional Planning Act grants permission to do so. Another element that affects the change of use is accessibility; because investors desire to invest close to the CBD, most residential homes nearby choose to convert to commercial use.

Political factors also affect how things are used, particularly when certain rules are altered and not many investments are made that would draw large amounts of money. Additionally, because the decision-makers are politicians, they may sway certain land uses to advance their political objectives. When these considerations have an impact on the change of use, the decision is taken in favor of the residential to commercial change of use.

The major effects of switching from residential to commercial use include both positive and negative ones, such as those on the economy (job opportunities, high rent prices, traffic congestion), the environment (noise pollution), and society (parking space, security), while the physical effects (uncontrolled settlements, uncoordinated land uses, aesthetics, mixed land uses, infrastructure overstretching, policy and regulation impacts) also play a significant role. The suggested feasible and useful solutions should be used to implement a shift in land use that is sustainable. The conceptual foundation for the conversion of residential space to commercial space is summarized in the Figure below :

Figure 2.6 : Conceptual Review for the study
 (Source: (Adapted from Raharjo, 2005; Egbenta, 2009; Asamoah, 2010; Sydney, 2012; Tomisi et al., 2016; and Gomna et al., 2016).

2.16 Regulation for operationalization of land pooling policy in India (Delhi 2014)

The land pooling policy will be based on the concept of land pooling wherein the land parcel owned by an individual, or group of owners is legally consolidated by transfer of ownership right to the designated land pooling agency which later transfers the ownership of the part of the land back to the landowners undertaking of development for such area. According to operationalize the policy and regulate the development following is laid down:

1. Economically weaker section (EWS) housing unit size to be ranging between 32-40 sqm.
2. Rainwater harvesting and wastewater recycling shall be mandatory with provision for storage for surface run-off water to improve the depleting groundwater levels.

2.16.1 Land pooling Policy 2018 (New Delhi, India)

Land Pooling is a new paradigm for the urban development of Delhi, wherein the private sector will play an active role in assembling land and developing physical and social infrastructure. Under this concept, owners or groups of owners will pool land parcels for development as per prescribed norms and guidelines, making them partners in the development process.

For integrated planning of a sector, the land required for the development of roads, utilities, greens, and other infrastructure shall be made available to the DDA and service-providing agencies for development as per approved Zonal Development Plan (ZDP) and sector layout plans. The planned development will increase the value of their land through the provision of infrastructure and public facilities.

The outcomes are expected to be world-class ‘smart’ and sustainable neighborhoods, sectors, and zones, planned and executed as per the availability of water, power, and other infrastructure. This policy is applicable in the proposed urbanizable areas of urban extension for which zonal plans have been notified.

2.16.2 Guiding Principles

- i. The pooling of land shall be done in accordance with sectors (as established in the Regulations) and zones (as defined in the Zonal Development Plans) under this policy.
- ii. The Policy is open to all landowners who own land, and any size of land may register and express their interest to participate as per the regulation.
- iii. To ensure unified planning, servicing, and subdivision minimum of 70% contiguous land of the developable area within the sector, free of encumbrances, is required to be pooled.
- iv. Of the pooled land, the Consortium will retain 60% and hold the remaining 40% on behalf of DDA, for the development of city-level physical infrastructure, recreational and public/semi-public (PSP) facilities as per the ZDPs and layout plan of a sector.
- v. Each landowner will surrender land proportionate to the area of land pooled, irrespective of land uses assigned to their original land in the ZDP.
- vi. The 60% of land shall be utilized by the Consortium for the development of residential, commercial, public, and semi-public facilities as per the Policy.
- vii. The Consortium will mutually decide on a formula for redistribution of developed land/ built space,- or any other form of fair exchange “Implementation Plan” with the consent of all landowners.
- viii. The final development of the 60% land shall be taken up by the Consortium. The 60% of land can be developed as separate sub-projects by those who have chosen to work as separate Developer Entities (DEs),

The DE can be (Should have pooled Minimum of 2 hectares):

- a) An individual landowner
- b) A group of landowners
- c) An entity (developer/ business/ corporate entity)

Note: The limit of 2 hectares has been set to ensure the adequate return of land for development.

- ix. Adequate provision of EWS housing shall be ensured in the new development area as per the Master Plan.

- x. External Development Charges (EDC) shall be applicable on the entire area of pooled land to cover the actual cost of providing city-level infrastructure.
- xi. Land parcels in a sector that remain un-pooled may be allowed to develop at a later stage:
 - a) Workability of the proposed layout plan in terms of accessibility and other functional requirements.
 - b) Making 45% of land available for city-level infrastructure/facilities
 - c) Payment of updated applicable EDC for infrastructure and services.

2.16.3 Role of DDA and/or Government

- i. Ensure smooth and fair implementation of the Policy.
- ii. Overall planning concerning ZDP and making provision city-level physical infrastructure, recreational, and public/semi-public (PSP) facilities.
- iii. Revision of ZDPs as and when required for new development areas, including delineation of sector boundaries.
- iv. Facilitation of the entire process of planning and development through a Single Window System for application, verifications, approvals, licenses, etc. in a time-bound manner.
- v. Overall monitoring of provision of relevant infrastructure for water supply, sewerage, drainage, power, transportation, etc.
- vi. Acquisition of any land, which has not been offered under the policy.
- vii. Ensuring the sale of EWS housing stock handed over by the DE/Consortium to DDA.
- viii. Setting up and operating a robust and credible dispute resolution mechanism to address grievances/disputes.

2.16.4 Role of the DE/Consortium

- i. A Consortium of constituent landowners will be created for unified planning, servicing, and subdivision/ share of the land.
- ii. Development and finalization of the Implementation Plan with the approval of all constituent landowners.
- iii. Preparation of layout plans and detailed site plans for the remaining 60% land as per the provisions of the ZDP and prevailing Master Plan.
- iv. Timely payment of External Development Charges (EDC) to DDA and service-providing agencies for developing public infrastructure and services, through the Single Window System.
- v. Seeking necessary approvals, inter-alia, of layout plans and detailed site plans.

- vi. Time-bound development of all internal roads and other related infrastructures such as water supply lines, power supply, rainwater harvesting, sewage treatment plants, water treatment plants, and parking including the provision of multi-level parking facilities.
- vii. Time-bound development and maintenance of the entire development including all the neighborhood level facilities i.e., open spaces, roads, and services until handover.
- viii. Time-bound transfer of the share of built-up space/land to constituent landowners/DEs as mutually agreed in the Implementation Plan.
- ix. Ensure the development of the prescribed built-up space/dwelling units for the EWS Housing component.
- x. Sell 50% of the EWS housing stock to DDA at a base cost prescribed by the latest CPWD index (plus the cost of EWS parking) or actual cost whichever is less. The DE/Consortium will develop such 50% housing stock as a separate block and provide all necessary parking, commercial and PSP facilities for this separate housing pocket.
- xi. Dispose the remaining 50% of EWS housing stock only to the residents within the new development, at market rates, to house community service personnel working for the residents/owners.
- xii. Bearing the cost of acquisition of land acquired by DDA as per law for the public purpose of ensuring the planned development of infrastructure in the Zones and sectors.

2.16.5 Norms for Land Pooling and Development Control Norms

The proposed land pooling and development by DE/Consortium shall be based on the following norms:

- i. The Land Use distribution at the city level for the urbanizable areas in the Urban Extensions adopted for this Policy is as under:
 - Gross Residential: 53%
 - Commercial: 5%
 - Industrial: 4%
 - Recreational: 16% (does not include green areas within the various gross land use categories)
 - Public & Semi-Public Facilities (PSP): 10%
 - Roads & Circulation: 12%
- ii. The above land use distribution will be split on a 40:60 basis. A minimum of 40% of pooled land is reserved for city-level infrastructure. A maximum of 60% of pooled land is available to DE/Consortium for development.

Table 2.5: Distribution of Land Use in New Delhi, India

Land use	Area of Pooled land	
	Minimum 40%	Maximum 60%
Gross Residential	--	53%
Commercial	--	5%
Industrial	4%	--
Recreational	16%	--
PSP	8%	2%
Roads and Circulation	12%	--

Source: (Regulation for Operationalization of Land Pooling Policy, New Delhi)

- iii. Sub-division of Gross Residential areas and provision of facilities (local and city level) shall be as per the Master Plan. Land requirements for the provision of neighborhood-level internal roads/ infrastructure/ services (including water supply lines, power supply, rainwater harvesting, STP, WTP, etc.) as earmarked in the layout plan will be met equitably by all the landowners/DEs.
- iv. 50% of the plots earmarked for neighborhood-level health and education facilities, within the Gross Residential Use (53%) in a sector, are to be returned to DDA for allotment to government agencies/ departments.
- v. Amalgamation and sub-division of city-level PSP plots as well as commercial plots shall be allowed. The DE/Consortium may also adopt innovative ways for achieving a vertical mix of uses (residential, commercial, PSP) within a building but in adherence to the prescribed additional development controls
- vi. Development control norms under the Policy are:
 - a) FAR for Residential, City Level Commercial, and City Level PSP shall be as per the prevailing Master Plan.
 - b) Residential FAR for Group Housing to be applicable on Net Residential land.
 - c) Net Residential land to be a maximum of 55% of Gross Residential land.
 - d) To provide EWS housing, the DE/Consortium shall utilize a mandatory FAR of 15% over and above the maximum permissible residential FAR.
 - e) EWS Housing unit size shall range between 30-40 sq.m.
 - f) Adequate parking shall be provided by the DE/Consortium as per MPD. In the case of the EWS housing component, a norm of 0.5 ECS/100 sq.m. of BUA shall be followed.
- vii. The Consortium/DE shall be compensated in the form of Tradable FAR, if it is unable to utilize the entire allowable FAR within the 60% land areas such as critical resources such as water, proximity to transport infrastructure, etc.

viii. Additional development controls for urban design, landscape, and built environment are to be notified as part of the ZDPs for land pooling zones. These controls will regulate building and site level aspects and promote sustainable environmental management systems through the integration of blue and green infrastructure in the sector layout plans.

2.16.6 Framework for Implementation of the Policy

- i. A website, to serve as a Single Window System, will be created to implement the Land Policy through online forms and protocols.
- ii. The detailed Regulations for operationalization of the Land Policy, including process and timeframe for participation, shall be formulated in a time-bound manner.
- iii. A two-stage Grievance Redressal Mechanism will be constituted within DDA to resolve all disputes and anomalies emerging from the implementation of the Policy.
- iv. DDA will create dedicated multi-disciplinary teams for managing site inspection, approval of alignments and site layouts, and other matters.

Source : (Regulation for Operationalization of Land Pooling Policy, New Delhi)

Land pooling Policy (New Delhi, India)

Figure 2.7 : Land pooling Policy Diagram of India

2.17 Rajasthan Township Policy, 2010 (Above 10 Hectares of Land)

To promote planned/integrated development of various towns by providing the basic infrastructure facilities and to safeguard the interest of the public at large by ensuring the availability of residential plots/houses at affordable prices, the State Government decided to review the existing Township Policy, 2002 and other policies and programs about urban areas of Rajasthan.

The layout plan of the various proposed schemes should have the planning norms of the land as detailed below:

1. Residential/ Commercial schemes Use Area of Percentage (Maximum 55% to 58%)

a) Plotted area / group housing / high rise

50% to 54% residential plotted area including a minimum 5% area reserved for EWS / LIG group housing or 15% of total No. of Plots/dwelling units to be kept reserved for EWS/LIG category. (Whichever is higher).

- 5% to 6% for commercial purposes (including informal sector shops). The commercial purpose can be petrol pump / multiplex / commercial malls / cinemas / tourism / any other general commercial.
- 10 small informal shops could be provided per 100 plots. The balance (out of 6%) percentage may be used for general commercial development.
- The sizes of the informal shops can be 6' x 6' to 10' x 10' which shall be reserved as informal shops/kiosks/ vegetable Mandi, Seasonal / Morning Market, etc.
- Informal shops shall be permissible on internal roads along with a minimum provision of parking in front of the informal shops, the percentage of land area used for parking in the planning shall be considered as a percentage of the plotted area (60%).

Public amenities like roads should be maintained without any reduction in the percentage of such parking requirements in the layout.

- (i) The EWS/LIG dwelling units/plots shall be compulsory in all township/mini-township schemes. At least 50% of houses are to be in the EWS category. In the case of flats the building specifications as mentioned in the Affordable Housing Policy, 2009 shall be followed.
- (ii) EWS/LIG plots and informal sector shops shall be allotted to a nominee of the developer or to the developer as in the case of other plots who in turn will allow the same to eligible persons in this category.
- (iii) For allotment of EWS/LIG houses/plots the income criteria as issued by State Government may be considered and the list of eligible and selected persons is to be sent to the concerned ULB.

- (iv) Size of EWS/LIGH plots - 30 to 45 sq.m / 46 to 75 sq.m. respectively and disposal of EWS & LIG plots shall be @ 25% and 60% respectively, of the residential price being charged from other allottees.
- (v) Size of EWS/LIGH flats to be - 325-350 sq ft and 500-550 sq ft respectively and disposal shall be @ Rs.750/- per sq ft or as decided by Govt from time to time

2. Facilities (Park & open spaces, schools, hospitals, etc.) Percent area (42% to 45%)

Normally, 20 -22% area would be utilized for the internal road network. In case sector road is passing through the scheme, it would be considered separately.

10% area reserved for open area/park in layout plan shall be allowed to be provided at different places subject to a minimum area of 3000sq.m at one place. On the remaining open area, construction of one Clubhouse will also be permitted. The plinth area of the clubhouse should be 10% of the open area plot and the permissible Built-up area of the clubhouse will not exceed 15% of the same.

Additionally, a minimum of 10% area for public utilities and facilities should be reserved and developed for public purposes like kindergarten schools. Welfare Centre, Dispensary, Hospitals, and other public use.

- (i) In no case, the open and facility area together shall be less than 20%.
- (ii) Internal roads shall not be less than 9 meters where the length of the road is up to 100 meters and not less than 12 meters where the length is more than 100 meters. In the case of the area used for EWS/LIGH housing the minimum road width can be 9.0 meters or lesser as provided in the Building Regulations/ Affordable Housing Policy 2009.
- (iii) In the case of commercial/institutional zones the minimum road width shall be 12 meters for a length of up to 200 meters and 18 meters for a length above 200 meters (except for larger commercial complexes for which wider road has been prescribed in the Building Regulations).
- (iv) The saleable facility area may be allotted to the developer at his request at the prevailing reserve price for residential purposes (in case this is not available the residential reserve price of a nearby area may be adopted). The developer shall develop the area for the purpose for which it has been reserved. In the event of the developer not being willing to take the land, the concerned ULB shall allot the same to others for the purpose for which it was reserved in the scheme.

Source : (RAJASTHAN TOWNSHIP POLICY-2010 (ABOVE 10 HECTARES), JUNE 2010)

2.17.1 Guidelines For Approval/Completion of Internal Development works In Townships

To ensure quality development, the developer must submit a Detailed Project Report (DPR) along with the application for approval to the concerned Urban local body. The following details are required in DPR.

- Layout plan showing details of the area proposed to be utilized for plots, roads, open space for a park, garden and playground, and other public facilities (like school, hospital, etc.)
- Details showing, the development in the surrounding area (at least 100 meters radius) along with its superimposition on sector plans (if existing).
- Estimate the expected population in the township and the requirement of amenities as per the prevailing standard approved by the Government.
- Details of internal development works as per specifications mentioned below
- Details of eco-friendly amenities to be provided.
- Plan showing HFL of major lakes, and water bodies, if applicable)

2.17.2 Technical Specifications for Internal Development Works

(a) Construction of Roads and Boundary Wall

- (i) Townships / Mini Townships may have a compound wall around the township with a gated entry/exit. However, in the case of any sector roads or public roads passing through the Township / Mini Township, the movement of the general public shall not be restricted.
- (ii) All the internal roads should be minimum of 9 meters where the length of the road is up to 100 meters and 12 meters where the road length is more than 100 meters and 18 meters where the length is more than 400 meters.
- (iii) However, as far as possible no row of plots should be more than 200 meters in length except the sector plan / zonal plan / main arterial roads having widths 18 M & above.

Note: Other Specifications of the roads shall be as per IRC norms.

(b) Power Supply and Street Lighting

- (i) In the Township / Mini Township scheme there should provide for a plot of land (approx. 1000 to 1500 sq. Mtrs. per 20 hectares) at a suitable location for the electricity authorities at no cost so that the electric sub-station for the township can be set up. The plot area will be considered in the facilities area of the layout plan.
- (ii) The development of electrification, power network, and power load requirement in any township/ mini township area shall be in accordance with the norms, rules & regulations of the State electricity agency. After the completion of the electrification work, the developer shall hand over the complete system to the concerned State electricity agency.

(iii) Streetlights - All the roads having a width above 24 meters shall have a divider, as well as the street poles, fixed on the divider having provisions of underground cabling. Other roads will have single light poles, erected on either side of the road. The distance between poles should not be more than 30 meters. The illumination levels of the roads shall be as per the standard of the local electricity company / National Building Code. After the completion of the street light work, the developer may hand over the complete system to the ULB / Local Electricity Company or any other maintenance company.

(c) Water Supply

- (i) All the water lines should be underground having a provision of providing connections to the plot-holder. The sizes of water pipes should be as per norms laid down by competent authorities.
- (ii) The township should have an underground water tank as well as an overhead water tank. The township should also have provision for Telephones, Gas pipelines, etc.
- (iii) The complete water supply shall be in accordance with the technical guidelines.
- (iv) After the completion of the water supply scheme, the developer may hand over the laid distribution and storage system.

(d) Sewerage & Drainage

- (i) All the plots in the Township / Mini Township scheme should be well connected with the underground sewerage line with proper slope, with the permission of the sewerage treatment plant (STP) in the Township / Mini Township scheme. The developer must establish and operate STP in the township. Recycling of treated wastewater for gardening and flushing (as per norms of the Environment) should also be provided for.
- (ii) The sewerage line should normally be located close to the boundary wall of the plots (within about 10 ft.) with a provision for connection from plots.

(e) Horticulture & Plantation

All roads should have plantation tree guards on both sides having a min. of two trees per plot subject to a minimum of 30 trees per acre of the gross area. Trees of heights more than 5 ft. should be planted. All the parks should be developed by the developer and maintained by the developer till the Township / Mini township scheme is complete and handed over to the ULB or the Resident Welfare Association / Society.

(f) Solid Waste Management

The developer must submit a detailed plan for the disposal of solid waste management and ensure its implementation till the Scheme is handed over to the ULB / Resident Welfare Body or any other entity.

(g) Rainwater Harvesting And Water Recycling

“Community rainwater harvesting structures” should be constructed by the developer and all water outlets and drainages should be connected in such a way as to recycle the water for gardening, washing, etc. after treatment. This should be strictly enforced by the ULB. Wherever feasible dual water supply system should be adopted by the developer - one for fresh water and the other for recycled treated wastewater

(h) Construction of Dwelling Units

The developer shall develop and construct at least 10 % dwelling units of the total units/plots in the township (more than 10 hectares) schemes.

(i) Solar Heating System

In the proposed scheme solar heating system shall also be provided as per the provisions of prevailing building regulations or as per the provisions in this regard made from time to time.

Chapter Three

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Methodology

The study methodology used in this thesis can be divided into three parts. The first part will deal with the identification of the issues and formulation of goals and objectives. Second, the literature review and formulation of an analytical framework comprise the theoretical part of the commercialization of a residential area derived from the study of numerous kinds of literature uses (books, journals, magazines, internet sources, photographs, maps, etc.) third, it will deal with the case study analysis, which includes a collection of primary data through various field survey, a questionnaire survey is also carried out to check the response of the city dwellers in order to assess the nature and extent of commercialization and resultant problems being faced by the people living in the land pooling area of Sinamangal and KII will also be conducted to the individual land pooling expertise, KVDA authority and planning authority. Finally, it concluded and recommend some key guidelines to develop the commercial area in the residential area in a planned way based on suggestions and best practices adopted in the other areas.

Thus, the thesis is organized into five chapters, the first chapter introduces the project brief and the needs of such project, and it outlines the commercialization context of the land pooling area Sinamangal including the scope and limitation of the thesis work. Moreover, it comprises the basic aims and objectives of the study. The second chapter is the literature review on the commercialization of residential units and its impacts based on different case studies all over the world. The third chapter includes the methodology involved in the research work. The theoretical framework, research paradigm, and methods used for the collection of data collections. The fourth chapter involves the analysis of the study area which involves the commercialization context and status of the completed land pooling area of Sinamangal LP area and it summarizes the evidence of the effects of commercialization based on the interview with the residents, customers, and owners of the commercial premises. It then discusses the weakness in the regulatory regime by providing a critical review of the policy and legislation relating to commercialization with the concerned authority including KVDA, Planning authorities, etc. The views of the regulators on various aspects of commercialization are then presented. The last section, five concludes the discussion along with key guidelines with an indication of measures required to effectively ensure sustainable commercialization in the metropolitan cities.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

The field survey has been carried out in selected land pooling planned housing schemes viz. Sinamangal land pooling is located at ward no 32 of Kathmandu metropolitan city. This case study area has been selected based on its location, representation of all the socio-economic groups of people, and because these are fully developed and occupied schemes under the Sinamangal land pooling project implemented by the then Kathmandu valley town development committee (KVTDC) which is now reformed as KVDA, the principal planning agency to plan and regulate development in the city.

The field surveys included segregation of the building according to their use such as purely residential, commercial, mixed-use or temporary commercial, etc. commercial land use survey, and interviews of residents, shopkeepers (doing business in a residential area), and residents are selected randomly in these settlements.

The study also critically reviews the Land pooling policy, development regulations policies, and guidelines regarding commercial use policies of the Nepal government and represent the real scenario of the developed LP area and purposed some insightful recommendation to the policy level and some key guidelines to improve the existing conditions of the area. Officials, planning authorities, involved stakeholders, and local government representatives exercising building and development control in these schemes have also been interviewed to consider the viewpoint of the regulators concerning the change in use of the residential Land pooling area into commercial hub and policy level strategies to control and improve.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual framework for change of use from residential into commercial
Source: (Mtawali, 2019)

3.3 Conceptual Framework as per the objective of the research work is as shown

Figure 3.2 : Conceptual Framework as per the Research Objectives

3.4 Research paradigm

The research paradigm is based on post-positivism approach. The study focuses on the commercialization of the residential neighborhoods originally planned and designed for residential purposes i.e., the land pooling techniques adopted by the government of Nepal. The research is based on inductive thinking. The research is based on qualitative and quantitative data collection. In the qualitative data collection, the research data is collected through the individual survey and Key informant interview (KII) by raising open questions.

3.5 Methodology Chart

Figure 3.3 : Methodology Flow Chart

3.6 Selection of Case study Project.

Out of the 14-land pooling projects completed till date (Gongabu, Dallu, Nayabazar, Gopi Krishna, Sinamangal, Sainbu, Lubu Bagmati Phant, Kamalbinayak, Liwali, and Sinitar) in the Kathmandu valley 5 of them located in the Kathmandu valley and three each in Lalitpur and Bhaktapur. (Joshi, 2020) The study area was selected such that there is an increase in commercial activities which can be observed in every major and minor street in the study area. The major commercial activities including restaurants, clubhouses, Fitness centers, Party palaces, Institution Buildings, etc. are growing haphazard in this area destroying the urban fabric of the planned area. Moreover, the goal, vision, and objectives of the LP area have not been met as planned to control and developed the planned area.

Chapter Four

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Study Area

Sinamangal land pooling is located at ward No.35 former and now ward no-32 in Kathmandu Metropolitan city. Though the total project area comprises 933-11-3-3 (ropani- anna-paisa-dam) land, the lalpurja of that place shows only 905-11-3-3 land area. The area has 14-8-0-0 of parti land and 9-11-0-0 is covered by road. After pooling the land, the total area will be 905-7-0-1 which will include 48-2-3-0 open areas having one large open space of land 14 ropani, and other two small open spaces of 6 ropanis each, 23 ropani for the treatment plant and road having 184-4-2-0 area including 8m and 6m roads and existing road.

After finishing the land pooling project, the 623-7-0-1 land area will be returned to the landowners, where the landowners will be able to do whatever, they want to. They may either use the land for farming or farming or for building construction or speculation of land. The rest of the area totaling 44-5-2-2 will be kept as the reserved plot from where the project can benefit by selling the land at the appropriate price.

The first phase of the sinamangal land pooling project has been completed in the first phase 707 ropanis of land have been developed whereas in the second phase 256 ropanies of land will be developed. Sinamangla land pooling 7 Gha comprises 226 ropanies of land. Sinamagal 7 Ka, Kha ,Ga and Gha and present KMC-32 had faced problem of haphazard construction. Previous to the land pooling project 20 houses without proper infrastructure and services were already present in the area. This scenario project possibility of unplanned and unmanaged development within the area making us realize the proper planning method have to be adopted at this site.

Boundary of Sinamangal

East – Sinamangal 7” Gha “ and Gothatar 8” ka

West – Tribhuvan International Airport

North- Nhykati VDC

South- Boundary of Pepsi-Cola and way to thimi

Figure 4.1: Location map of study Area
(Source: Author)

4.2 Summary of Study area

Project Name: Sinamangal

Location: KMC Ward no 32

Starting year: 1995

Completion Year: 2003

Duration: 8 years

Area(ha): 35.1

No of holding: 964

Contribution: 32.6

Commercial: 7

Residential: 67

Min. (m²) plot size: 80

> min. (m²) plot size varies

Management committee headed by a mayor

Legal basic: TDC Act 1988

There is a plot description of altogether 1707

Household numbers – 1074

Mohi numbers – 410

Unregistered plot – 43

Assumed Households: 1074, assumed family size 5.6, assumed population: 6015, assumed density: 171.49p/ha

Minimum plot size: 2.5 annas (80 sqm.) and maximum plot size: 6-4-3-3.97)

Open spaces: 5 no's (5.3%)

Road category: 8m,6m,4m,2m

Water supply: Proposed to be implemented after completion of Melamchi project

Electricity: NEA

Telecommunication: Implemented by NTC.

1st phase completed on 707 Ropani

2nd phase on 225 ropani.

The land areas consist of small streams, kulos, and roads making the land visually bigger than it is.

Map of Study Area

Figure 4.2 : Map of the Study Area
(Source: Author)

4.3 Purposes of Sinamangal land pooling project

- To control the increasing unmanaged urbanization.
- To fulfill the ever-increasing housing demand.
- To develop housing plots with proper services by the minimum investment of the Government of Nepal.
- To make the local public aware and active in the process of modern urbanization.
- To make planned development possible in modern urbanization.

- To create a healthy and hygienic housing environment.
- To propose uniform development within a certain area.
- Indirectly help in the employment of the local people.

(Bajracharya, 2063)

4.4 Sinamangal Nagar Samaj

The objective of the Sinamangal Nagar Samaj is to make the Town planning area a clean, green, peaceful, and secure community. It was formed to control, support, and coordinate the development works, including construction work, and recreational and empowering the community to develop environmentally friendly surroundings. It was registered on 24/10/ 2058 B.S. in District Administrative Office (DAO), Kathmandu (Registered no: 646-058/59). The amendment was done in 2074 B.S.

Every permanent resident of the planning area can be a general member by paying Rs.200 and renewing annually. The committee of 23 people has been formed with 5 people holding the major responsibilities whereas the other 18 members represent form each block as per the block size.

4.4.1 Aims and objectives.

- To make it easy and convenient for the community and develop a concept of a smart city
- To develop Greenery Households and neighborhoods.
- To make hygienic and clean streets and nodes
- Peaceful, secure, and well-informed planning area
- Coordination and cooperation with the different stakeholders to make the sustainable area.

4.4.2 Some Major responsibilities and Duties to be accomplished

- To Make provision of at least one Dustbin in the shops.
- To have a 2-planting pot in front of every shop
- The residential area facing the problem of noise pollution, dirt, air pollution, bad smell from different grills, furniture, aluminum factory, kabaddi, and storage area of sand, stone, aggregate, etc. needs to be controlled.
- To control and stop the high-volume horn and sound, over speed of the vehicle, and not allowing heavy vehicles on a residential road.
- Not allowing the street vendors, storing and vehicle parking in the street, and making the easy access to the pedestrian.
- To control the throwing of plastic bags, cigarettes, and other items on the streets.

4.4.3 Proposed works

- Focusing on developing the parameters of the smart city.
- Control pollution and mitigation.
- Greenery, clean, safe, gender and disabled friendly safe and secured development of open space.
- Management of the open space.
- Coordination for improving road, light, and sewerage systems.

4.5 Infrastructure of Sinamangal LPP

Following is the infrastructure available in the study area of the Sinamangal land pooling area

1. Transportation
2. Access Road
3. Drainage
4. Sanitation
5. Water supply
6. Energy

a) Transportation

Nepal Yatayat with around 30 buses running from the area and provided great help to the residents. This route is also used by the inhabitants of the green city apartment. It has good access to road and transportation facilities with good connectivity to the surrounding neighborhood.

b) Access Road

The project has roads of different widths 6m, 8m, and 11 meters. Most of the roads have been pitched and a few roads need maintenance work. The interior residential roads are used by the people and the vehicles as a bypass road to connect the main highway to Thimi and other places. Due to the high volume of traffic flow, these roads are dusty. There is still no provision for streetlights and traffic management.

c) Drainage

There is a stormwater provision from the project in the land development area. House owners are required to build a septic tank for the toilet waste collection so that they could not discharge the sewer into the drainage. The project has envisaged building a reed bed filter plant in the 23 ropani of land in the southeastern sector of the project. But as the cost of the land is very high it decided to abandon the project in favor of the mechanical treatment plant that occupies a relatively smaller space.

d) Sanitation

Solid waste is collected by privately run solid waste disposal company. It utilizes cycle driven vehicle for collection from door to door and the average charge for this is about rate Rs. 300 per month. The waste is separated into sellable items and dumping items. People in the area can contribute by reducing the waste volume and managing the biodegradable waste for manure formation (like using compost bins) thereby contributing towards environmental protection. Similarly banning the use of thin plastic bags in the area can contribute to the solution of drainage clogging by bags.

e) Water supply

The major problem in this area is the unavailability of a reliable supply of water adequate which is readily accessible to consumers. In the area, there is no provision for piped water. According to the project office, the water supply will be available only after the completion of the Melamchi project. The people of the area use underground water through boring and well for domestic use. Some use the stone waterspout.

f) Energy

For lighting and heating, there is a supply of electricity from the Nepal Electricity authority. For this purpose, the project has been doing cooperation with NEA. Till now there is no provision of streetlights in some of the houses solar energy has been utilized for heating water by using solar panels.

4.6 Land use of Sinamangal (Before, and after land pooling, and in the year 2079).

Table 4.1: Description of land use before LP

S.N	Land Description	Area (R_A_P_D)	Area (Sq.m.)	Percentage (%)
1.	Residential Use	6-7-0-0	3276.69	0.91
2.	Agricultural	507-11-3-3.35	258443.26	71.79
3.	Vacant	176-12-3-3.75	89997.07	25.00
4.	Road	9-11-0-0	4930.93	1.37
5.	No man's land, stream, Rajkulo, etc.	6-9-0-0	3340.31	0.93
6.	Total	707-3-3-3	359988.26	100

Table 4.2: Description of Land use after LP

S.N	Land Description	Area (R_A_P_D)	Area (Sq.m.)	Percentage (%)
1.	Residential Use	519-15-2-1	264530.95	74
2.	Open Space	34-0-1-2	17309.09	5
3.	Road	147-0-2-2.8	74806.25	21
4.	Total	701-0-2-1	356644.63	100

Chart 4.1: Pie chart showing Percentage of Land use before LP

Chart 4.2: Pie chart showing Land use after LP

4.7 Area-wise Land Category

Table 4.3: Developed Residential land according to Area

S.N.	Area	Nos.	Remarks
1	0-2-2-0	146	
2	>0-2-2-0 & < 0-4-0-0	441	
3	0-4-0-0	4	
4	>0-4-0-0 & > 0-8-0-0	378	
5	>0-8-0-0 & > 1-0-0-0	196	
6	>1-0-0-0	86	
	Total	1251	

Chart 4.3: Bar chart showing land category according to area

According to the Nagar bikas record, there is a residential land of 6-4.3-3-3.97. Maximum plots are provided between >0-2-2-0 & < 0-4-0-0 which is suitable for small medium housing in the case of Sinamangal LP.

4.8 Housing Development Scenario from 2002 to 2022

Figure 4.1: Housing Development in study Area 2002
(Source: Google)

Figure 4.2: Housing Development in study Area 2012
(Source: Google)

Figure 4.3: Housing Development in Study Area 2022
(Source: Author and Google)

4.9 Existing land use

Figure 4.4: Existing Land Use of Study area 2022
(Source: Author)

Table 4.4: Distribution of Land use of year 2022

S. N	Land Description	No. of Buildings	Percentage	Remarks
1.	Residential Use Only	602	51.32%	
2.	Commercial use only	152	12.96%	
3.	Mixed-use building	241	20.54%	
4.	Temporary Commercial use	150	12.79%	
5	Under construction	7	0.6%	
6	Schools	21	1.79%	
7	Total	1173		

Chart 4.4: Pie Chart showing existing Land use of 2022

Out of 1251 developed residential plot, 1173 residential plot has been utilized for different purposes. which is 93.76 % has been occupied and only 78 residential plot is left which is 6.24 %. Different commercial activities available in the town planning residential area are as follows:

1. Institutional building
2. Banks
3. Complex
4. Clothing Store
5. Gold
6. Cooperative building

7. Furniture shops
8. Dish
9. Pharmacy
10. Club
11. Dance Bar
12. Restaurants
13. Meat shops
14. Cosmetics
15. Grocery shops
16. Shoes
17. Bag shops
18. Liquor
19. Dairy
20. Mobile repair service center
21. Automobiles Repair
22. Hardware and sanitary
23. Electrical
24. Flower shops
25. Spa
26. Boutique
27. Fitness center etc.

Figure 4.5: Commercial and Mixed used in Study Area.
(Source : Author)

- The above figure illustrates that commercial activities flourished on the main road as well as the secondary or residential road.
- The temporary commercial is also high in number in this area. Temporary commercial areas are 1-2 stories made of up CGI sheets or truss structures. It has commercial activities like clothing stores, grill factories, furniture factories, aluminum stores, hardware and sanitary, etc. many more.
- Almost every corner or street of the area has a large and pure commercial building affecting the residential neighborhood.

4.10 Analysis of institutional building in the Study Area

Figure 4.6: Location of Institutional Building
(Source: Author)

Table 4.5: List of schools in Study Area

S.N	Name of the Schools	Remarks
1	Bal Batika Schools	
2	Nexus International Schools	
3	Pritima English Schools	
4	Career Building International Academy	
5	Kids International Schools	
6	Gateway Montessori Schools	
7	Liberty Public Schools	
8	Gateway Academy	
9	Mangala English Schools	

10	Global Public Schools	
11	Global Montessori Schools	

There are altogether 11 educational institutions buildings i.e schools and colleges available in the study area. Most of the schools are rented and are in residential buildings. They are located haphazardly in the residential area. Most of the schools do not comply with the minimum criteria of school guidelines. There is also an insufficient area for playgrounds and residential buildings beings converted into schools which is much vulnerable during the disaster.

Figure 4.8: Buffer created 150m of Institutional Building
(Source: Author)

Figure 4.8: Circle of Radius 400m From the center.

The above figures show the three are the presence of at least one school within every 150m radius from one school. Although private schools have been developed for business purposes.

- Residential buildings with narrow staircases and high occupancy can be a risk to the children. The no. of schools as compared to the total area and population is more.
- According to Clarence Perry neighborhood concept there is need of 1 school in every 800m radius i.e., 1 or 2 school is enough in this area.
- There is no provision of supervision and monitoring from the Municipality level, ward level, and governmental Education institution on the quality of education and the facilities and services provided by the schools despite having a high payment for school fee.

4.11 Respondents' Profile

Figure 4.9: Respondents Distribution of Study Area
(Source: Author)

Chart 4.5: pie Chart Showing Respondents Gender and ownership of House

Chart 4.6: Pie Chart showing Building category

Figure 4.10 : (a) Residential, (b) Commercial and (c) Mixed-use Buildings samples

- Out of 1173 built Households, 10% i.e., 121 nos of households were surveyed randomly in the Sinamangal LPP. About 17 questions were asked to the respondents answers are below.
- Out of 121 randomly selected respondents 72% of them are male and 28% are female.
- Among the respondents 91% of the respondents were landlords and the remaining 9% are tenants.
- 64% of the respondent have their houses built for residential purposes, 25% for mixed-use, and 11% for commercial use.
- Most of the residents have moved to this year between 2050- 2060.

4.12 Price of the land

The price of the land has so much fluctuated in recent decades. Especially in the land pooling area, the price of the land has increased significantly after the land pooling is done due to the availability of the different infrastructures and facilities.

Table 4.6 : Price of Land in different year

S.N.	Road Length	Road Type	Price in 2056-2058	Price in 2059	Price in 2061	Price in 2063	Price in 2079
1	4m	Graveled	10 lakhs/Ropani	15 lakhs/Ropani	20 lakhs/Ropani	2.5-3 lakhs per anna	45-50 Lakhs per anna
2	6m	Graveled	13 lakhs/Ropani	20 lakhs/Ropani	25 lakhs/Ropani	3.5-4 lakhs per anna	50-60 lakhs per anna
3	8m	Graveled	18 lakhs/Ropani	25 lakhs/Ropani	30 lakhs/Ropani	4.5-5 lakhs per anna	70-80 lakhs per anna

(Source: (Bajracharya, 2063)), Author)

Chart 4.7: Bar Chart showing price of land in Different year from 2056 to 2079

The above graph shows that the price of the land has increased 16-17 times than the price of land in 2063 during the period of 16 years i.e., each year land price has increased double the price of 2063. The land price has gone out of control and it's mainly due to the mediator or land broker agent (dalal) who keeps on increasing the land price to increase their profit as well as the landowner. The land price has gone to an optimum level and needs the proper guidelines and to control the haphazard increase of the price of land in the planned area.

Chart 4.8: Bar chart showing residents moving to this area

The above bar chart diagram shows that During the survey it has been found that 62% of people have bought their land and shifted to this area in the year between 2055 to 2060. Whereas 20.66 % of people have bought their land and shifted to this area in a year from 2060 to 2070. 16.53% of people have shifted to this area between 2070 to 2079.

- It is found that most of the original landowners have sold their plots which were more in the years 2055 to 2060. During this period the original landowner had sold their plot for a short-term profit.
- It has been found that most of the original landowners of the planning have sold their plots which shows the displacement of the original landowners. (98% are out of area).
- Recent research by Nepal Rastra Bank shows that land prices are rising at a rate of 27.7% annually and doubling every 3.5 years. Similarly, according to Nepal Land and Housing Developers' Association, a real estate consultant, the land prices in the valley rose nearly 300% from 2003 to 2008

- The rate of growth and increment is completely different. And this price increase has proven irrational in many locations. A plot in Baneshwor costs 1.25 crore per anna, while Durbar Marg costs more than two crores an anna. It will cost about 5.6 crore rupees to develop a 4000 square foot rental building on a four anna Baneshwor land. To service the interest and investment funds at 12%, you need Rs. 560000.00 every month, or Rs. 140.00 per square foot. In the current situation, this price is extremely excessive. And it is really difficult to even imagine making money off of that. This is the situation in the important business area. (1ropani.com, n.d.)
- The number of households in Nepal's cities without access to housing is growing as a result of rising real estate costs. The working poor has been most seriously affected by the urban housing crisis.
- The government's incapacity to control this sector and its unwillingness to implement new housing policies may ultimately lead to an increase in the number of homeless individuals sleeping on the streets.
- The land price and housing cost have been increased such that the housing for all does not seem to be met. Even in the Land pooling area, there is no housing provision for the poor and low-income groups, as a result, these low-income groups of people shift to other places causing sprawl.

4.13 Satisfaction with the change and increase in the commercial activities

Chart 4.9: Pie Chart showing satisfaction with change in use.

58% of the respondents are not satisfied with this change and the increase in commercial activities in the residential area. Whereas 42 % of the respondents are satisfied or ok with the change. Moreover, Out of 11 tenant respondents 82% of the tenant are satisfied with the change whereas out of 110 respondents 46% of the house owner are satisfied with the change in use. The households near the commercial area or the houses along the main streets and doing commercial activities seems to have satisfied with the increase of commercial activities but the households expect this area does not want the commercial activities.

- Some of the reasons for not shifting to the other place or area found during the survey are as follows
 - i. This land pooling area is still better than the other organically developed or unplanned developed areas for residential purposes with the availability of open spaces, and infrastructures, and better in terms of facilities and services available in this area.
 - ii. Most of the respondents have adjusted to the situation and changed their surroundings.
 - iii. This area is still having less noise pollution and is well managed than the other area of Kathmandu.
 - iv. Good transportation access and easy and convenient availability of the goods and services in the locality.
 - v. Well-managed system and good and peaceful living environment.

4.14 Want to shift to another place

Chart 4.10: Pie chart showing people want to shift to other places.

- Despite having less satisfaction due to the change and increase of the commercial activities. Only 14% of the people want to move to the new area and 86% of the respondents still want to live here. i.e., they are not interested or plan to shift to the other area. It's because there is no other place to shift, and they think that this planning is still better than the other place in Kathmandu valley.
- Some of the few reasons for the people to shift to the other area are as follows.
 - i. Due to the attachment of the schools with the residents' houses. The continuous and frequent noise coming from the schools located near to their houses causes noise pollution and causes disturbance in the day times.
 - ii. Due to the Pepsi factory and the noise coming from the factory. The Pepsi factory shifts their goods at nighttime causing disturbance during the day and night.
 - iii. Due to the haphazard placement of the schools' institutions, different temporary and permanent commercial activities such as furniture factories, grill factories, storehouses, nightclubs, dance bars, party palaces, etc. frequently create noise and overcrowding.
 - iv. Due to the noise pollution caused by the football ground at the center.
 - v. Due to the mismanagement of the systems and facilities people want to shift to the new place for a peaceful environment as their expectation has not been met.

4.15 Major Factors for an increase in Commercial Activities

Chart 4.11: Bar chart showing factors for an increase in commercial use

Table 4.7: Factors and Ranking of commercial use

S.N.	Variables	Mean Score	Ranking	Rating
1	Profit maximization	4.5	1	Very High
2	Population Growth and Demand	4.33	2	High
3	Lack of government Regulation	3.95	3	High
4	Strategic Location	3.81	4	High

From the above graphs and Ranking from the mean score, profit maximization is the major reason for the increase in commercial activities followed by the population growth and Demand of the community. Lack of Government regulation is ranked 3rd for the increase in commercial activities followed by the strategic Locations.

- Due to the increase in commercial activities the land value, as well as the property value, has been increased due to the availability of different goods and items. The rental value of the property has also increased due to the demand of the people to rent the space for different commercial activities. During the survey, it has been found that the rent price near to commercial activities area is relatively higher than in the other places.

- Population growth and demand are other factors for the increase in commercial activities. It is obvious that population growth demands different activities to support their livelihood and always demands more from the area where they live. Increased population growth demands more commercial activities to survive. People started different commercial activities to earn their living as a result rampant commercialization activities appeared. Moreover, the increased population growth survives these businesses and demands more as a result of new and different commercial activities in the area introduced and settled.
- Lack of government regulations and monitoring encourages and motivates people to start commercial activities in the residential area. They started operating the commercial activities without having proper provisions and facilities to support the commercial activities. There are also weaknesses in planning regulations including a lack of a master plan, and not following planning norms and standards while extending infrastructure.
- The strategic location has also supported this area in an increase in commercial activities. It is located in the area at the back side of the airport and has very good connectivity with the other areas with good transportation facilities. It is also supported by the Sun City apartment which is close to this area. The people of sun city apartments have also supported sustaining the commercial activities in this area.

4.16 Effect of increase of Commercial Activities

Chart 4.12: Bar chart showing the effect of an increase in commercial activities

Table 4.8: Effect of an Increase in Commercial activities and mean score and Ranking

S.N.	Variables	Mean Score	Ranking	Rating
1	Increase property Value	4.3	1	High
2	Overcrowding	4.2	2	High
3	Disturbance	4	3	High
4	Increase in Traffic Congestion	4	3	High
5	Parking Problem	3.95	4	High
6	Security Risk	3.85	5	High
7	Renovation of the House for commercial use	3.25	6	Moderate
8	Relocating new Place	3	7	Moderate
9	Limited Space for Residential	3	7	Moderate

From the above survey data and mean value score increase in property value is the major effect due to an increase in commercial activities followed by Overcrowding and Disturbance and an increase in traffic congestion has the same effect and is ranked 3rd whereas the parking problem is the next effect. Security

Risk is ranked as 5th followed by the Relocating new place, limited space for residential purposes, and renovation of the house for commercial use.

- Due to the increase in commercial activities in the study area the property values have increased significantly. The price of the land and the building has skyrocketed. The low- and middle-income family cannot afford the property in the planned area. The rent has also risen high due to the demand for the building to operate the different commercial activities such as restaurants, financial institutions, Dance clubs, educational institutions, clothing stores, etc., and many more. The vacant land is also leased to develop commercial activities at high rental prices.
- Another effect of an increase in commercial activities is overcrowding of the people in the area. for business purposes and employment opportunities, people from different locations reside there for business purposes with their families. The floating population is high.
- Disturbance is another major effect faced by the people. Sound from the different dance bars, pubs, restaurants, educational institutions, party palaces, etc. creates continuous and loud sounds in the community disturbing the peaceful environment of the society. As well as the sound coming from the Pepsi factory also caused the problem for the residents near it. Bypass of the heavy trucks and other vehicles through the residential area and loading and offloading of the long and heavy trucks in the store factory produced sounds and sirens during the day and nighttime causing sound pollution. Most of the street vendors' stalls are selling the thing in front of the residential housing gate causing problems and disturbance.
- Traffic congestion and the parking problem is other effects of an increase in commercial activities. Most of the commercial activities buildings do not have parking facilities in their arena as a result of the customer parking their vehicles on the road causing traffic congestion. Most of the vehicles are parked on the road and the traffic flow is disturbed.
- Renovation of the Houses for commercial use is the increasing trend if the commercial activities are not controlled then the house for residential purposes will decrease. Most Households have started to convert their house from residential to commercial. While using the residential house for commercial purposes the owner will receive more rent than renting it to the family. If it is not controlled, then it will be a serious problem for the LP area.
- As it has also been found by the survey that the vision and mission of the planning area are not clearly mentioned to the people and has not been met, if the continuous rise commercial activities, and high rental and land price will create the people to relocate to the new place. the low- and middle-income people will not be able to sustain themselves in this area.

- The more space used for commercial activities overall reduced the residential space. Housing stock will be reduced to a large number and increase the commercial space.

4.17 Positive Impact of Increase in Commercial

Chart 4.13: Bar chart showing the positive impact of commercial use

The survey and above bar chart reveal the benefits of an increase in commercial activities. 93% of the respondents think that it optimized the value of the property, 95% people it is easy and convenient goods and services, 96% people believe they have to travel less, and 97 % of the people think that increase in the commercial activities has created the employment opportunities to the people, 81% of the people think it has contributed to local government taxes, 18% of the people think it has made the street safer, 2% of the people it will contribute to an influx of new residents and 13 % people think it will attract quality stores and restaurants.

The study reveals that the change in use of residential into commercial use is greatly influenced by numerous factors which were ranked according to their mean values index benefits of an increase in commercial activities are:

1. Employment opportunities
2. Less travel
3. Convenient goods and services
4. Optimization value of the Property and

5. Contributing to Local Government with Taxes
6. Safer street
7. Attracts quality stores
8. Influx of new residents
 - The increase in commercial activities in the study area has created employment opportunities for people living in the area. People from the nearby area also come here for a job to work at different institutions, to operate the business, etc. The high demand for commercial activities has created opportunities for people to operate their businesses such as restaurants, cafés, clothing stores, etc.
 - Due to the availability of the goods in their locality they don't need to the other area for example new road area to buy the necessity goods. It saves their time and traveling distance to the CBD.
 - They do not need to move to other areas to find the goods. Almost every item is found in the area from clothes to shoes, restaurants to dance clubs, fitness centers, liquor shops, hotels, etc.
 - The increase in commercial activities has contributed to the government by paying the tax. According to the prevailing rules, the tax for the residential property is Rs.25 per sq. ft and for the commercial and mixed-use is Rs. 35 per Sq.ft. Though the increase in commercial activities increases tax for the government the availability of facilities will be reduced or will have pressure on it.
 - Increase the rental as well as the property value of the people. Commercial activities have also played a vital role in increasing the price. Due to the commercial activities, there is a high flow of people for different activities which makes the area more vibrant and familiar to the people.

4.18 Negative Impact

Chart 4.14: Bar chart showing the Negative impact of commercial use

The survey data and the above bar chart revealed that 66 % of the people think it has a security risk due to an increase in commercial activities, 88% of the respondents think that disturbance is caused, 71% of the people think that Parking is the problems, 74% of the people think that traffic congestion as the problem, 84% of the people respondents overcrowding as the problem, 68 % of the people think high rental and property value, 31% people think that it has caused the problem in the infrastructure and only 17 % people have respondents chaotic development as the problem.

The top 5 Negative impacts due to the increase in commercial use from the survey are as follows:

1. Disturbance
2. Overcrowding
3. Traffic congestion
4. Parking Problem
5. High rental and property value
6. Security Risk
7. Infrastructure problem
8. Chaotic Development

- Due to the increase of the commercial activities in the residential area, there will be an overflow of the people in the commercial area causing the overcrowding of the people. The unnecessary and continuous sound produced by the different activities in the area has created a disturbance to the people and destroyed the peaceful environment of the residential area.
- Due to the unavailability of the different facilities to support the commercial activities user the consumers are forced to park their vehicles in the street and narrow down the street, especially in Infront of those commercial activities' areas. Due to the lack of parking provision available in the commercial area.
- The people will be ready to pay high rent and price for the property if it is close to the commercial area due to the high potential of the area to be valued more and will be receiving the more rental price.
- Due to there is also the security risk, there is a high flow of people with a variety of intentions. there is a high risk of a thief, fighting, excessive use of alcohol, etc.
- There is a problem in the electricity having high voltage consumed by the commercial area, the frontage of the house and road are occupied by the commercial activities, high consumption of water and insufficient road width for the commercial use causing the problem to the overall infrastructure of the area.
- The development is chaotic. The propose and intent of the land pooling have not been made there is haphazardly placement of the institutional buildings, schools, party palaces, restaurants, etc. There is a school in the middle of the residential areas. Unregulated and unwanted commercial activities are also increasing and encroachment of the residential area by the commercial activities.

4.19 Planning Authority Interview Output

- They are not satisfied with the development of commercial activities in the residential area.
- Due to profit maximization motives and population growth commercialization activities are increasing.
- Other planning parameters need to be considered and need to be planned in LP area.
- To control the haphazard development, need to prepare proper urban design guidelines, development regulations and by-laws needs to be separate for the LP area.
- These Land pooling are small in scale and still learning always in pressure due to financial status and had not think of for future demand and necessity.
- Lack of awareness in people and weak monitoring policy.

- Local government should give priority to develop the LP area in a planned way.
- LP area issues should be handled by the Local level without change in purpose according to the need of the local people.
- The remaining budget from the project needs to be provided to the local government for improvement of LP area.

4.20 Land pooling Objective and Achievement

Table 4.9: land pooling visions and other aspects considered in LP project.

S.N.	Vision of the land pooling	Does LP Project Fulfill	Comments
1	Control the increasingly unmanaged Urbanization.	N	Small Scale and only a few in Nos. implemented.
2	Full Fill ever-increasing Housing Demand	N	No mandatory provision for EWS Housing
3	Develop housing plots with proper services by the minimum investment of the Government of Nepal.	Y	Housing Plot developed but converted for other purposes.
4	Make the local public aware and active in the process of modern urbanization.	Y	Involvement of people in LP but no clear understanding of vision of LP
5	Make planned development possible in modern urbanization.	N	No consideration of planning parameters.
6	Create a healthy and hygienic housing environment	N	Increase in the Commercial activities
7	Propose uniform development within a certain area.	N	Haphazard Development.
8	Indirectly help in the employment of the local people.	N	No provision for employment.

4.21 Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis of data obtained from this research work, the survey reveals the following major findings using the objectives

- The study reveals that the current trend of land pooling system used in the Kathmandu Valley is restricted to land development techniques with the formation of residential plots, street networks, block size, and open space hierarchy where the developed land plot will have the regular shape of land along with vehicular access to each plot and successful only in financing basic urban infrastructure but it had not considered the other dimension of the urban planning not linked with the buildings and their uses in the plots and forecasted the future demand and necessity.
- It has been found that the increase of commercial pressure will create people to modify or add space for commercial activities, which will encourage them to make changes to the occupancy and not obey

building bylaws which will cause different problems at the community level and raise a concern about the people safe and will be more vulnerable from the disaster perspective.

- This land pooling scheme mainly focused on the residential aspects and depended upon the city center or adjacent districts for other types of urban services, the recent development is more comprehensive and provided a higher standard of commercial, service, and educational facilities of their own and perhaps employments sources as well. Hence, this needs to be adjusted and need to be planned during the planning of the Land pooling project.
- The study finds that the commercial land uses along the access roads of any size even in the interior residential areas like eateries, retail stores, restaurants, supermarkets, and banks among others generates traffic congestion, parking problems, noise pollution, poor sanitary environment and thus, degrades the quality of the existing residential facilities.
- There is a rampant increase of commercial activity taking place in the residential area over the past few years, up to date it is ok in society if it is not controlled then these haphazard commercial activities will force the inhabitants to shift to the new area in search of a peaceful living environment.
- There is still 21.53% area to be developed including the temporary commercial used area, if the 15% area is developed for purely commercial use then the area will be populated by commercial activities and will create a lot of problems in the community and the scenario will be worse.
- The land pooling area have a 6m and 8m road width, people have an understanding that the 6m road is for residential purpose and 8m road width for mixed-use and commercial use.
- Planning authority and the other concerned stakeholder should take care of the future trends of commercial activities which need to be forecasted and should be planned in the planning phase of the project.
- If the trend of the rampant increase in commercial activities is not controlled then the outsider will be needed to consume it, and the inhabitants will not be enough to consume all the goods and services, Hence, new, and different innovative, and more intense commercial activities will be added in the future in this area.
- The profile of the residents has changed from the middle class to the higher class. The price of land and housing cost is (skyrocketing) beyond the reach of the low- and middle-income group of people. This will ultimately makeshift the people to other places causing urban sprawl.
- However, in planned or haphazard growth areas, the provision of infrastructure is on an incremental basis without any planning.
- Recent development scenario of the land pooling area will make a failure of the land pooling project if the immediate actions are not taken at the planning level as the development of the area will be more

haphazard with the haphazard placement of the commercial activities, high and uncontrolled price of the land and house in the land pooled area, etc.

- Commercial sign boards have almost covered the front façade of houses. The municipality is mainly concerned with collecting taxes rather than regulating such signage. The weak enforcement of building regulations is clearly seen in the construction of high-rise structures in the planned area.
- It is believed that more than 90% of the buildings in urban Kathmandu do not follow the prevailing building regulations. Such transformation is seen not only in increased building floors (and hence density) but has also been found in use from residential use to mixed-use with commercial activities on the lower floors and residential in the upper part of the buildings.
- In addition to these, ordinary residential houses are being converted into schools, nursing homes, and training institutes (mass gathering activities) without assessing their structural capabilities.
- Nonetheless, from another perspective, land pooling projects can be an opportunity to demonstrate the capability of local government in utilizing local resources and building community in the weak of financial constraints to make LP area a better arrangement cohesive development with consideration of inclusivity, sustainability, and resilient city.
- Land pooling is the project where the KVDA authority is involved especially the urban planner, Urban Designer so this planning authority needs to think more than arranging the road layout and blocks. If so, then the concept of a smart city, a new city, and a sustainable city can be fulfilled once we can develop the planned city in the LP area.
- The use of LP projects for large-scale urban development has been severely constrained by the absence of comprehensive master plans and development control at the city (and Valley) level, as well as the lack of alternative mechanisms for their use. In this case, the LP is ineffective as a tool for establishing a safe and livable urban environment. Financing the projects other than selling the reserve plots.
- The prevailing building regulations have inadequate clauses to regulate change in building occupancy, urban signage, and haphazard vertical division and renovation and reconstruction of them. It is not clear what sort of built form is intended from the prevailing building bye-laws.
- People of the Nagar committee want the KVDA to clear the mission vision of the planning.
- People want that it will be good if the residential area became residential with a mixed-use and planned commercial areas only in a particular place.
- There are so many loopholes in the development controls laws which must be taken care of first to plug and enforce them rightly so that the city does not grow haphazardly in the future and change in occupancy is controlled.

Chapter – 5

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The study investigated the change of use from residential to commercial in the land pooling area Sinamangal (Town planning) originally designed and planned for residential purposes. It is well established that the area is experiencing change and is under the pressure to increase the commercial activities in the residential area. As there we can see the competition between the commercial and residential uses with the residential, which can have positive and negative impacts.

The dwelling located at the major strip line of the street as well as the interior streets leading to the resident's house have been intruded by commercial use or intensive mixed-use and the number of commercial places has increased resulting in decreasing the residential property. According to the study's findings, factors that contributed to the abrupt shift in usage from residential to commercial were profit-maximizing brought on by the increased demand for commercial space uses, a lack of government regulations, population expansion, and demand.

Moreover, the results of this study are consistent with those of other researchers who found that excessive commercial activity concentrations had negative effects on residential areas' environmental quality, including noise pollution, traffic congestion and accidents, security threats, aesthetic appeal, disturbance, overcrowding, parking problem, and high rental and property value in the residential areas, as well as challenging in land use control measures and contributing to deficits in the housing stock. It ultimately encourages the urban sprawl of the low socioeconomic group of people due to the high and unregulated price of the property in the land pooling area.

Despite having some benefits of the increase of commercial activities such as Employment opportunities, Convenient goods and services which reduced the travel time and optimization of the property value, etc. found by the study. The area needs to be developed as a purely residential area with allocated space for mixed-use and fixed controlled commercial use. The aims and vision of the land pooling area i.e., to make a suitable peaceful living environment for the people must be met. If the raising pressure on commercial land use is not controlled and maintained the commercial land use will be sprawling all over the area contributing to the rapid decaying of the planned area (urban fabric).

However, taking into consideration of the negative consequences of use change and the need to meet up the current economic realities and land pooling aims and objectives, the land pooling area needs to allocate to the specific development zone so that the land pooling is developed in a planned way with controlled and

managed commercial activity. There needs to be a strong legal framework and monitoring to control the haphazardly increasing commercial activities.

5.2 Recommendation

Nonetheless, several problems and issues have been identified from the study and analysis made. The following recommendations are put forward in the form of a policy strategy, to enhance and improve the existing practice of land pooling and control the haphazard development of the commercial activities used in the land pooling area and guide them in the realization of their goals and objectives.

5.2.1 Insight at Policy Level

- Land pooling area should be designated as a "comprehensive development zone". Then, planning standards and guidelines should be created for a better urban environment in terms of the layout plan, street network, provision of open space, and other amenity requirements, such as urban design and building construction guidelines. When used at each specific LP site, these criteria can be further improved based on the site setting and project nature.
- Land pooling areas should be accompanied by well-articulated planning briefly that should reasonably allot specifies adequate space for commercial, industrial, and recreational activities and should incorporate the other parameters of the planning schemes with adequate facilities and services for their performances considering the inclusivity and sustainability of the city.
- Involvement of the private sector or developers should also be allowed to execute the land LP projects with clear regulating guidelines and planning standards including infrastructure detailing with flexibility.
- Land pooling projects should be financed or subsidized by either central government, province-level government, or by the local municipalities, or by three tiers of government besides the contributions from the benefited landowners. The present contribution of 30% of land by landowners is just sufficient to provide a road network and limited open space, which is not sufficient to create vibrant and lively residential neighborhoods.
- Numerous government agencies working at different layers such as the Ministry of Urban Development (at central level), Kathmandu Valle Development Authority (KVDA– valley level), Municipalities (city-level), and Local Ward Office (ward level) in coordination and cooperation with the professional bodies (Regional and Urban Planning Society of Nepal – RUPSON, Society of Nepalese Architects – SONA, and Nepal Engineers’ Association – NEA) and people engaged in building industry should prepare a comprehensive master plan and zoning regulation with clear vision and objectives of Kathmandu city (and Valley) level. The knowledge and experience of the key players on land pooling

and land use should be broadened, especially on the possible factors responsible for the change in land use in urban centers and how better the land pooling projects can be executed with achieving a desirable urban environment.

- Many line agencies responsible for urban infrastructure provisions such as road, sewer system, telephone, and other utilities seem often working with little coordination and cooperation they need to be integrated and coordinated in the process of the LP project. The design of infrastructure and services capacities should be prepared and anticipated to meet the densification of the newcomers - population growth - demands - when dealing with the fast growth of commercial places. This effort is to maintain the quality of the neighborhood, society, settlement, and environment. As a result, the future demand and needs are forecasted properly and fulfilled.
- Strengthening the managerial and technical capabilities of Kathmandu Valley Development Authority and local municipalities is essential. The weak institutional arrangement, shortage of trained human resources, and poor financial base all have constrained the local municipalities to take control of haphazard growth in the LP area. The same case is true for KVDA.
- There should be the provision of timely and regular field monitoring and supervision of the land pooling area to enhance the development control and enforcement process including penalties for defaulters.

5.2.2 Recommendations

- Most of the commercial and institutional (Schools, colleges, Hospitals, Clinics, stores, offices, etc.) are operated in residential buildings without having their structural vulnerability assessment and required services and facilities they need to be discouraged and need to be well monitored by the local Government.
- The commercial activities should be organized, planned, controlled and supported by making provision of necessary infrastructure services such as good access roads with parking facilities, potable water, electricity, and employment schemes.
- The residential area facing the problem of noise pollution, dirt, air pollution, foul smell from different commercial activities such as grills, furniture, aluminum factory, kabaddi, and storage area of sand, stone, aggregate, etc. which needs to be controlled and banned.
- The remaining 21.53% of land should be developed in a planned way and only selective commercial activity should be permitted selectively and carefully, taking into consideration community needs, environmental impact, and provision for safe and easy traffic circulation and adequate parking.
- The mandatory development controls regulations such as building bye-laws are statistics and cannot address the dynamic nature of society, city, and fast-changing lifestyle and city economies. Hence, instead of relying on those mandatory rules, Urban design guidelines can be prepared to address the

site context and present-day needs as well as to regulate major streets, buildings, building setbacks, urban signages, material requirements, and detailing. These guidelines are not mandatory and are prepared under the consensus of participating stakeholders and in many cases, they are linked with incentive mechanisms to encourage individuals to follow design guidelines and fine system which will help to achieve the best desirable options.

- Most of the implications due to change of use such as overstretching of infrastructure, lack of parking space, and abuse of planning standards can only be overcome through the preparation of a new Integrated Development Plan (IDP) and Local Area Plans by the KVDA, Urban planning council, and Local government. These plans will serve as a guide to the developments in specific areas, especially concerning the issue of land use planning. Therefore, the need to begin the preparation of IDP for the land pooling area.
- The stakeholder in urban land management should introduce a database of real estate property transactions through one door system so that it is easier to monitor and ascertain the actual situations of the real estate transactions and so that the property price can be controlled.
- There is a need to begin the use of the Geographical Information System (GIS) to create spatial data for updating Properties that have undergone the process of change of use so that they can be controlled.
- Local Government should allot some budget to the LP area so that concerned authority would be able to adequately monitor and control land use changes in the city; because it has been revealed in the survey that the local authority faces challenges in monitoring land use change developments due to several factors, among which is lack of adequate finances.
- A better social control and awareness system is recommended, encouraging people to actively participate in managing commercial spaces. Due to the success of socializing the issue, a community association's function should be expanded. To encourage community engagement in this issue's management, both among native residents and non-native or newcomers, healthy social norms and connections should be upheld and strengthened, along with the household sector's role.
- No proper street is defined whether it is for the footpath or the vehicle. If the road of 6m is for pedestrian purposes it is better to do stone paving than the pitched surface simply separating and making realized that this is for the pedestrian priority street.
- No boundary wall in the residential area so that the area is more vibrant.
- To control and stop the high-volume horn and sound, over speed of the vehicle, and not allowing or restricting the heavy vehicles on a residential road.
- Not allowing the street vendors, storing and vehicle parking in the street, and making the easy access to the pedestrian.
- Controlling the throwing of plastic bags, cigarettes, and other items on the streets.

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Appendix-I: Questionaries

QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire's aim is to study the Change from residential use into commercial Use in the Pepsi-Cola town planning area. The questionnaire survey is purely intended for academic purposes to enable the student to research and write his thesis dissertation in partial fulfillment of the Masters's Degree in Urban Design and conservation at Khowopa Engineering College, Bhaktapur. Your assistance and contribution by responding to the questions honestly and promptly will be highly appreciated.

Note: This questionnaire is strictly for academic purposes and will therefore be treated as confidential and no information will be divulged to any third party.

Research Questions

1. Name of the Respondents:
2. Category of the Respondents:
 - a. Landlords
 - b. Tenants
3. Building Space used for floor-wise
 - a. First Floor
 - b. Second Floor
 - c. Third Floor
 - d. Fourth Floor
 - e. Fifth Floor
4. In which year you were shifted to this area?
5. When did you build the house?
6. What was the land Price /house rent at that time?
 - a. Land Price per anna
 - b. House Rent (Per sq. ft)
7. Recent land price/House rent

- a. Land Price per anna.....
- b. House Rent (Per sq. ft)
8. What was the purpose of constructing the building?
9. Have you noticed increasing commercial activities in the last 10 years? Yes [] No []
10. What are the reasons for the increase in commercial activities increase?
.....
11. Are you satisfied with the changes in the neighborhood? Yes [] No []
12. Common Factors Responsible for increase in commercial activities. Please tick only one ranking option in this section as applicable. (Key: SD- strongly disagree, D- Disagree, N- Neutral, A- agreed, SA – Strongly agreed)

S.N	Common factors for Commercial activities increase	SD	D	N	A	SA
1	Increase demand for commercial premises due to population growth	1	2	3	4	5
2	Profit maximization motive of the commercial land users	1	2	3	4	5
3	Lack of government policy and regulations	1	2	3	4	5
4	Easy accessibility and strategic locations	1	2	3	4	5
5	Others	1	2	3	4	5

S.N.	Effect of increase of commercial activities	SD	D	N	A	SA
1	Increase in traffic congestion	1	2	3	4	5
2	Limited space for Residential space	1	2	3	4	5
3	Increase in land/property/rent price	1	2	3	4	5
4	Relocating to new place	1	2	3	4	5
5	Security Risk	1	2	3	4	5
6	Disturbance (Noise pollution)	1	2	3	4	5
7	Overcrowding	1	2	3	4	5
8	Parking Problem	1	2	3	4	5
9	Renovation of the house for commercial use	1	2	3	4	5
11	Increase economic activities in residential zoned area	1	2	3	4	5
12	Others(.....)	1	2	3	4	5

13. Select the five positive impacts of the increases in commercial activities?
- a. Optimize value of the residents' property.
 - b. Less travel and easy access / Not move out of (shop out of) their neighborhood
 - c. Convenient goods and services
 - d. Employment opportunities
 - e. Contributing to local government with taxes
 - f. Safer streets
 - g. Contributing to an influx of new residents to the city.
 - h. Attracts quality stores and restaurants with lots of potential.
 - i. Others
14. Select the major five problems faced.
- a. Security risk
 - b. Disturbance (noise pollution)
 - c. Traffic congestion
 - d. Parking problem
 - e. Overcrowding
 - f. High rental and property value
 - g. Infrastructure problems
 - h. Lost sense of community/ social problem by heterogeneous people
 - i. Illegal/Chaotic development of the area.
 - j. Others (specific).....
15. Do you plan to move to other places because of the increase in commercial use taking place in your area? Yes [] No []
- a. Reasons.....
16. What is the primary reason that is likely to force you to relocate from the area where you are currently staying to somewhere else?
- a. Because rent has become too high
 - b. The area has become congested and commercialized.
 - c. Other (Please specify)
17. Do you have any suggestions or a wish about this area?
-

Thank you

Appendix -II: Photographs

Commercial Buildings in the Residential Area

Commercial use in study area

Building Renovation and Temporary structure

Some Commercial Activities in study area

Field survey and Interview with Government Authorities ,KVDA, Ward office.

